

Interconnected
Nord-Est Innovation
Ecosystem

Via VIII Febbraio 1848, 2 - 35122, Padova
CF 92315730280 | Cap.Soc. Euro 100.000,00 i.v.
Email: info@consorzioinest.it
PEC: consorzio_inest@pec.it

Cross-cutting activity 1: Support to the generation and the development of start-ups and spin-offs

Leader:
Ca' Foscari University
of Venice

INTRODUCTION TO THE CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITY 1 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES.....	2
1. SPOKE 1 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1	7
2. SPOKE 2 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1 (6 pages).....	10
3. SPOKE 3 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1 (6 pages).....	18
4. SPOKE 4 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1 (6 pages).....	26
5. SPOKE 5 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1 (6 pages).....	35
6. SPOKE 6 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1 (6 pages)	42
7. SPOKE 7 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1.....	50
8. SPOKE 8 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1 (6 pages)	53
9. SPOKE 9 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1 (6 pages)	62

Finanziato
dall'Unione europea
NextGenerationEU

Ministero
dell'Università
e della Ricerca

Italiadomani
PIANO NAZIONALE
DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA

INTRODUCTION TO THE CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITY 1 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES

iNEST CC1 goal is to develop a feasible and functional framework, to support the generation and development of start-ups and spin-offs in the North-East of Italy ecosystem.

This peculiar ecosystem has an interesting tradition especially in family-run small to medium size entrepreneurship, and remarkable results in academic research.

Nevertheless, if compared to international benchmarks, it can still grow both in terms of proactive contamination between science and entrepreneurship stressing the innovation factor, and in a stronger investors' interests in startups.

Leveraging on the iNEST project framework, consisting of topics and RTs - the project pairs them with spokes and universities, and then clusters them in smaller ecosystems, while in reality they come to be widespread in the North-Eastern territory -, the CCI tasks (Pre-Acceleration, Acceleration, Fundraising) help academic and guiding research institutions interact among themselves and with the regional context, with the ultimate goal to contribute to regional development through continuous exchange and synergic on-the-field work.

Spoke	RT	Description	Spoke	RT	Description
1	RT1	Safety and quality of life in mountain Environments	6	RT1	New Digital Technologies
	RT2	Resilience of Mountain production systems and supply chains		RT2	Data Analytics
	RT3	Decentralization of mountain structures and infrastructures		RT3	Sustainable Business Models
		RT4		New Narratives and Communication Strategies	
2	RT1	Digital Health and Systems for the citizens	7	RT1	Business models for sustainable agri-food at different levels
	RT2	Biotechnologies and Pharmaceutical Technologies		RT2	Process/product innovation for sustainable agri-food
	RT3	Devices for Health		RT3	Circular economy
	RT4	Food and Health		RT4	Logistics, supply chain and vertical coordination
3	RT1	Energy	8	RT1	Biology of hydrosphere ecosystems
	RT2	Smart Manufacturing, Mechatronics and Robotics		RT2	Physical-chemical risks and impacts on the hydrosphere
	RT3	Materials		RT3	Sustainable waterway mobility
	RT4	Artificial Intelligence and Data Science		RT4	Land-sea integrated maritime and spatial Planning
	RT5	Organizational, economical and legal aspects		RT5	North Adriatic Digital Twin
			9	RT1	Mathematical, numerical and data-driven modeling
				RT2	Model Order Reduction
				RT3	Automatic learning for Digital Twins
				RT4	Applications of DT in industry, medicine, Environmental sciences, daily life

Spoke	RT	Description
4	RT1	Strategic plan for the development of the construction and sustainable design sectors
	RT2	Technological solutions for the construction and sustainable design sectors
	RT3	Interaction between environments & human beings in the construction & sustainable design sectors
5	RT1	New and Emerging Technologies for Human Centric Manufacturing and other industrial working environments
	RT2	Digital Twin in Industries 5.0
	RT3	People, organization, and processes for Industry 5.0
	RT4	Personalized Assistive Technologies & Smart Environments for Inclusive Living in private & public spaces

Therefore, within this picture, for the design implementation of an innovation ecosystem - functional for the generation and the development of research start-ups and spin-offs -, it is considered strategic to enable the development of this cross-cutting CC1 tasks, that deeply involve all Spokes.

A sum-up of iNEST CC1 tasks' status can be described as follows:

- **CC1.1: Planning and validation:** planning was completed in March 2023. Validation and periodical reviews are ongoing till the end of the project
- **CC1.2: Pre-Acceleration:** ongoing (first Pre-Acceleration round: November 2023 - March 2024)
- **CC1.3: Acceleration:** first development of the Acceleration Framework and engagement and coordination of the Key Actors; the implementation of the Acceleration phase will start at the end of the first Pre-Acceleration round (task leader: UniVR)
- **CC1.4: Fundraising:** yet not started (task leader: UniTS)

As far as the activities' outputs are concerned, a comprehensive sum-up of overall **results** achieved as of January 2024 within the **CC1.2 Pre-Acceleration task and subtasks** is:

- **Development of the Pre-Acceleration framework:** a scouting system has been designed for iNEST CC1, providing a common strategy, a standard process and shared tools to the 9 Spokes, enabling customised implementations according to each Spoke peculiarities (i.e.: different open calls engagement methods, as well as contact collection / selection, and first approach to scientists / researchers; how start-ups have been chosen and implemented). Key actors have access to an online repository where all the common documents, minutes and tools are progressively shared and stored;
- **Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (CC1.2.1):** all the Spokes have been engaged and trained both individually (since Oct 1st by the Scouting Officer with operational support of the two Scouting Assistants, involving Scouting Specialists, while they have been progressively enrolled) and all together as a unique team (plenary Scouting Specialists, 14/12/2023) on the common goals, state-of-the-art scientific literature, strategies, processes and tools. Weekly personal reviews / debriefings have been done to share these topics. A minority of Spokes has not yet officially appointed their Scouting Specialist, and is currently managing the tasks with internal personnel (Spoke 1, UniBZ; Spoke 4, IUAV; Spoke 5, UniPD) for specific reasons that will be illustrated in each Spoke report;
- **Implementation of the Scouting Stage to develop entrepreneurship from the universities' ecosystems and drive the research efforts towards a proof-of-concept (CC1.2.2):** the

designed scouting system is in the first implementation round. The engagement of the target groups is proceeding in a decentralized way, with each Spoke collecting ideas from students, researchers and early stage startups (third mission and others linked to universities) using a custom approach, and in synergy with the internal initiatives led by Technology Transfer and IP Valorization. Engagement mechanisms are: events, calls for ideas, targeted meetings and communication activities. Calls for ideas, open engagement initiatives were also launched online by Spoke 6, Spoke 8, Spoke 9. Each Spoke deals with the pre-screening idea collection and guides the emerging ideas / startups, supporting the first submission and filling in a more detailed Form, when ideas are structured. The Selection Form is suggested as centralised - to favor convergence and the funnel approach - and was developed by the Scouting Officer's team together with a Pitch Deck template, according to the guide of the program Leader and Manager. The Pitch Deck template offers the chance to explode a set of evaluation criteria that will be defined and used by the CCI Committee (possibly taking into consideration of the advice given by a panel of sector experts and professional investors (i.e VCs)) to skew the number of startups and select the ones that will access the Acceleration phase.

Target n. of applications to the Call (by March '24): 100+ for each round (min 10 per Spoke)

Current number of applications / ideas / early stage start-ups collected is **90+**

- **Implementation of the basic online entrepreneurial training to provide a standardized model through the ecosystem (CC1.2.3):** open access international benchmarks of entrepreneurial education have been reviewed, after a selection, and then made available to the Spokes in a common shared online space. All the applicants have access to online entrepreneurial learning materials. The chosen benchmark for the learning objects is Stanford business school: <https://startupclass.samaltman.com>. Key themes of the online publicly available lessons are: how to get started, how to raise money, how to build products, and how to grow. Further custom learning objects to train the applicants on the preparation of a Pitch Deck are being finalized and will soon be released by the Program Leader, Prof. Carlo Bagnoli. Other Spokes are available to contribute with some more clips.
- **Open innovation activities (CC1.2.4):** The Open Innovation Manager in charge of this task will provide a specific report completing this mid-term deliverable.

On the other hand, general outcomes from the cross cutting perspective are the good practices in dialogue settings among different Spokes, with the related common procedures and tools in Pre-Acceleration activities that have been shared.

Then, for the encountered problems and related actions in the cross cutting perspective, some reflections could be proposed:

1. Because of the specific scientific-communication background of the persons involved, Communication activities for CCI have been directly addressed and supported by the Event Communication Specialist and Assistant (Sissa, Spoke 9), according to graphic settings generated by luav, Leader of Spoke 4;
2. Public tenders to be opened, and contracts to be signed of Scouting Specialists missing: on this side the Program Leader and Manager are in close contact with the different Spokes, to share the importance of this key step and to complete the team;
3. Plenary meetings review (19/10/2023, CCI Committee, online; 27/10/2023, CCI Program Leader with Spoke 3, 4, 6, 8, 9, at Polo Alto Adriatico; 30/11/2023, CCI Committee, online) have helped to interpret and implement the complexity of the project. Thus, the decision making process has been consolidated and a common approach for phase activities and tasks has been decided, adopting
 - a bottom-up course of action, to empower the methodological and practical experiences rooted in the single Spokes, in order to support a process that enables innovative ideas to be turned into research start-ups and spinoffs. The proactivity of single Spokes will boost commitment and, at the same time, help ideas and future potential entrepreneurs (students, PhDs, researchers, scientists etc.) to emerge;
 - a top-down approach, for the planning of Acceleration & Fundraising phases, that will define the business model and the organisational basic processes for the research start-ups and spin-offs, as well as the investment rounds to get those to enter the market and consequently scale up. A governance of these standardised and structured phases will enable beneficiaries to focus on their core job: entrepreneurship. Upcoming processes will then be disseminated to all Spokes.

Next steps to be met in the cross-cutting perspective are:

- Analysis of scientific-based entrepreneurial ideas through targeted interviews: the best ideas/startups will be evaluated by the Committee and then will move on to the Acceleration phase;
- Choice and sharing of start-up selection criteria, using the Pitch tool enabling convergence (Committee);
- March 19th (Selection Day): common, plenary event organisational setting, especially in terms of next steps for the engagement for the ecosystem / the actors of the ecosystem;
- Decision on the weight and distribution of hybrid approach within the Acceleration phase, eventually enrolling dedicated consultants involvement, with related mentoring process to be set up.

References for the cross cutting perspective are in the link to the common shared [Drive](#) environment.

1. SPOKE 1 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1

Creating a startup is an exhilarating and daunting venture that requires thorough planning, strategic decision-making, and relentless determination. In today's fast-paced and highly competitive business landscape, it is crucial for aspiring entrepreneurs to engage in various activities that can pave the way for a successful startup. The Free University of Bolzano has worked to create a team that can support such activities, before focusing on internal resources and then on hiring external personnel. The internal group is composed by three professors, one RTD-B, one RTD-A with different background and competence on ideation and market research to assessing funding options; producing business plans; and delivering new products to the market. The external positions have focused on identifying the right format to attract solid specialists in setting start up structures, via a complex roadmap, in order to convert brilliant ideas into viable businesses.

1.1. SPOKE 1 CCI OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

(title of the task, brief description of the topics, participants, general organisation and planning, expected results)

Title: Ecosystems for mountain innovation

The Free University of Bolzano leads the activities of the Spoke 1 “Ecosystems for mountain innovation” and develops research and technology transfer activities in the interdisciplinary area of mountain ecosystems. The main general objective is encouraging the development of new products, processes, and lifestyles capable of consolidating or supporting local traditions that guarantee the survival and demographic vitality of the mountain contexts from any standpoints (economic, environmental and social).

In the CCI activity, the objectives of the Free University of Bolzano to identify scouting specialist and startup analysts. A scouting specialist acts as a strategic advisor, providing critical information and insights to guide decision-making for the startup. They help the startup to identify and capitalize on emerging opportunities, technologies, and partnerships that can contribute to its growth and success. The startup analyst plays a crucial role in providing financial insights, analysis, and recommendations to support the startup's growth and success.

The Free University of Bolzano has created a group of five professors with specialization on scouting specialists, on ideation and market research to assessing funding options; producing business plans; and delivering new products to the market.

For the startup analyst, the Free University of Bolzano has studied the best contract possible for hiring experts with relevant experience and motivation to deliver the tasks.

1.2. SPOKE 1 CCI TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

List of CCI Tasks:

- CCI.1: Planning and validation
- **CCI.2: Pre-acceleration**
 - Sub Task CCI.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 9-40
 - Sub Task CCI.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 10-23
 - Sub Task CCI.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 12-26
 - Sub Task CCI.2.4: Open innovation activities. the objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners in order to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs and co-innovation activities between universities, startups and companies.
Responsible: UNIUD
Duration: months 9-40
- CCI.3: Acceleration
- CCI.4: Fundraising

List of Spoke 1 RTs

- RT1A : Safety and quality of life in mountain Environments – Mountain Social Life
- RT1B: Safety and quality of life in mountain Environments – Mountain Habitat
- RT2: Resilience of Mountain production systems and supply chains
- RT3A: Decentralisation of Mountain Structures and Infrastructures – Energy Strategies
- RT3B: Decentralisation of Mountain Structures and Infrastructures – Logistic Strategies

Focus on Task CCI.2: Scouting and pre-acceleration activities in the Spoke 1

Background / State of the Art: the state of the art of the unibz cross activities component CCI has been focused in team building and recruitment of external personnel. At the same time, a call is going out to unibz academic staff for the selection of potential start-ups and entrepreneurs to be supported within our activities.

Methodology: as mentioned above, through a call for applications we intend to reach out to all academic staff at unibz to solicit their participation in the proposed support course in CCI activities.

Ongoing activities: recruitment is encountering problems of compatibility between internal unbiz regulations and the compatibility with counselling activities reportable within the iNEST project. But we are working to fix this problem.

1.3. SPOKE 1 CCI DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

(e.g., conferences, meetings, participation in kick-off and mid-term plenary sessions, overall working group activities, interaction with the stakeholders)

The Free University of Bolzano has started to study interaction with the stakeholders to actively searching for startup ideas. Among the initiatives, the group has proposed to have an internal call for proposal from all the academic network of the Free University of Bolzano.

1.4. SPOKE 1 CCI MAIN RESULTS

(main results achieved till now, including pictures, photos, graphs, table, link to on-line material, etc...)

The Free University of Bolzano has created a group of five professors with specialization on ideation and market research to assessing funding options; producing business plans; and delivering new products to the market. The Free University of Bolzano has studied the best contract possible for hiring experts with relevant experience and motivation on creating and developing startups.

1.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

The definition of the best contract has been difficult. The standard post-doctoral position has been too limited to receive candidatures with experiences in the analysis of the startup projects. Different forms of contract, based on appalti o collaborazione diretta. The two options have benefits and drawbacks. An extensive analysis with lawyers and administrative has been initiated and it should be concluded at the beginning of 2024.

1.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

(With reference to the 2024 activities)

The next steps of the 2024 activities relates to complete the team with startup analysts. The team will work on identification and analysis of successful practices of generation and development of research start-ups and spin-off among the INEST Project Partners. The team will help to identify the valuable startups and prepare the initial documents in the acceleration phase. This is functional to the development of a framework for the project activities build around a common shared nucleus while retaining space for personalization to accommodate individual SPOKES specificities.

The challenges refer to build a team that can interact on a regular basis with other SOPKES and with other projects inside the SPOKES.

2. SPOKE 2 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1 (6 pages)

Spoke 2 activities focus on applied research and technology transfer related to the areas of health, wellness and healthy eating. These thematic areas are declined in the Spoke in a broad sense, including the related enabling infrastructures, both physical and digital, and the digital transformation of companies and entities operating in the related supply chains.

The Spoke's main mission is to enhance technological development and social innovation to promote the health and well-being of citizens and support the digital and green transition of the Triveneto social and health system. The Spoke will pursue this ambitious goal by combining the study, development, and testing of enabling sciences and technologies in various fields: from artificial intelligence to digital health, biotechnology, omics, electronics, and robotics. The project will not only deal with technology, but will properly take into consideration the relevant social, historical, economic and psychological context. The technologies developed will be integrated to contribute to the digital transformation of the socio-economic system in the Northeast, promoting innovative cures and treatments that can contribute to a healthy lifestyle and monitoring their impact on citizens and their quality of life.

Within the context of a citizen- and patient-centered framework, the objective of Spoke 2 is to foster technical and social innovation with the purpose of enhancing human health and well-being, as well as providing assistance to the transition of Triveneto health systems to digital and environmentally friendly practices. The ambitious overarching aim will be pursued by Spoke 2 by the utilization of enabling technologies and sciences, which include Artificial Intelligence, Digital Health, Biotechnology, Omic Technologies, Electronics, and Robotics. This will be done within the framework of social, historical, economic, and psychological factors. In order to contribute to the digital transformation of the socio-economic system of the Triveneto region, technologies will be incorporated. This will involve the promotion of innovative treatments and therapies for a healthy lifestyle, as well as the monitoring of the influence these technologies have on inhabitants and the quality of life they experience.

Within more specific reference to the Cross Cutting activity 1 – Support the generation and the development of research start-ups and spin-offs, the Spoke 2 promotes itself as a catalyst inside the university system to foster the creation of startups initiatives with business ideas related to health, food, and lifestyle. The is an important player in the context of innovation ecosystems, offering access to advanced research resources and aiding the incubation of breakthrough ideas.

The goal is to create real impacts in the form of new processes, products, and services that will strengthen the iNEST Ecosystem. The projects produced focus not just on issues of research and technology innovation, but also on assisting emerging businesses in developing innovation strategies. Spoke 2 strongly encourages the use of digital tools and technology in this context, including them into both research and development efforts and the new goods and services that come from them. This combination between academic research and entrepreneurial spirit within the institution generates a dynamic ecosystem that fosters the development and growth of new firms, contributing considerably to the innovation landscape.

2.1. SPOKE 2 CCI OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

(title of the task, brief description of the topics, participants, general organisation and planning, expected results)

Title: Cross-cutting Activity: Support the Generation and Development of Research Start-ups and Spin-offs [CCI] for the **Spoke 2:** Health, Food and Lifestyle

Research Topics: RT1 – Digital Health and Systems for the Citizens; RT2 – Biotechnologies and Pharmaceutical Technologies; RT3 – Devices for Health; RT4 – Food and Health

Participants: Prof. Alessandro Rossi (Spoke 2 CCI Principal Investigator and Rector's Delegate on Business Support); Prof. Sandro Trento (School of Innovation - SOI Director); Prof. Erica Santini (Department of Economics and Management, Delegate for Internationalization); Prof. Andrea Caputo (Department of Economics and Management, Director of the Master in International Management); Prof. Diego Ponte (Department of Economics and Management).

General Organization and Planning: At the University of Trento, key activities within Spoke 2: Health, Food, and Lifestyle will be a strategic mix of scouting and acceleration activities, aligned with the overarching design of an innovation ecosystem that supports the generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs. This approach is characterized by a dual structure:

Firstly, the Pre-Acceleration phase will be managed in a decentralized yet coordinated manner across all SPOKES. This structure is essential for generating and selecting innovative ideas that can evolve into research start-ups and spin-offs. The decentralized aspect of this phase allows for direct support to emerging entrepreneurs, including students, PhD candidates, and researchers. Simultaneously, coordination across SPOKES ensures the replication of economies, the development of methodologies, and the creation of technological platforms that are applicable to all SPOKES, drawing from the best cases at each university.

Secondly, the Acceleration & Fundraising phases will be centrally managed. This phase is crucial for defining the business model of the research start-ups and spin-offs and managing investment rounds to facilitate market entry and scaling. Centralized management during these phases allows for economies of scale, utilizing methodologies and technological platforms that have been developed and tested.

At the University of Trento, the contribution to these phases will be twofold: local scouting activities will be carried out via a scouting specialist who will focus on identifying and nurturing promising ideas within the university. Additionally, the centralized acceleration activities will be supported through startup analysis, ensuring that the transition from idea to market is as smooth and efficient as possible, thereby enhancing the potential for successful market entry and growth of these ventures.

Also, the local research group will engage in regular meetings to coordinate efforts and ensure alignment of objectives. Additionally, regular interactions are planned with ecosystem stakeholders, including HIT and Trentino Sviluppo, as well as with other iNEST CCI research units. This collaborative approach is designed to harness diverse expertise and resources for effective innovation and entrepreneurial growth.

Expected Results: The expected results include the successful establishment of an operational framework for innovation, the development of a skilled and informed pool of innovators through the execution of various awareness and pre-acceleration programs, and the effective identification and nurturing of potential startups and spin-offs in the subsequent acceleration and funding stages. This collective effort aims to result in tangible advancements in the research and development of health, food, and lifestyle-related technologies and solutions.

2.2. SPOKE 2 CCI TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

List of CCI Tasks:

- CC1.1: Planning and validation
- **CC1.2: Pre-acceleration**
 - Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 9-40
 - Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 10-23
 - Sub Task CC1.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 12-26
 - Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities. The objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners in order to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs and co-innovation activities between universities, startups and companies.
Responsible: UNIUD
Duration: months 9-40
- CC1.3: Acceleration
- CC1.4: Fundraising

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and pre-acceleration activities in the Spoke "2"

Background: a series of initiatives at Unitrento are concerned with raising awareness on innovation and entrepreneurship among students and scholars. Central to these efforts is the School of Innovation (SOI), which offers interdisciplinary training blending technical, scientific, and humanistic approaches to innovation. The SOI's curriculum, enriched by the Crash Course in Intellectual Property Rights, equips participants with essential knowledge for ideating, validating and protecting innovation.. Also, through initiatives like the Business Design program and the Start-Up Lab, participants gain practical skills in market analysis, business strategy, and human-centered design, laying a strong foundation for entrepreneurial ventures. The Proof of Concept (POC) program is reserved for patent holders and supports the efforts towards translating theoretical knowledge into viable, market-ready initiatives. Collaboration with Hub Innovazione Trentino (HIT) further strengthens the university's capacity in technology transfer and innovation, bridging academic research with market opportunities through the participation in the Trentino Startup Valley program. These programs collectively act as a springboard for scouting and pre-acceleration activities, preparing participants not just in ideation but also in the practical aspects of launching and scaling innovative solutions in the competitive market of health and wellness.

State of the art: The theoretical and practical basis of Trento University's entrepreneurship and innovation activities are founded on a wide range of scholarly works and practice-based theories. This includes, but is not limited to, key contributions such as Lombardi and Berk's thoughts on "Startup Program Design," which provide useful frameworks for organizing entrepreneurial acceleration and incubation programs. Eric Ries' 'The Lean Startup' is another good example, demonstrating the importance of constant innovation in the entrepreneurial process. Additionally, among other resources, Steve Blank's 'The Four Steps to the Epiphany' and 'The Startup Owner's Manual,' co-authored with Bob Dorf, serve as significant tools, providing extensive strategies for starting and maintaining successful companies. In practical terms, in the above mentioned programs and initiatives, the university incorporates approaches such as design thinking, which encourages creative problem-solving and user-centered product development. The lean startup methodology and its validation concepts are critical in fostering a culture of quick prototyping and iterative testing, which is required for rapidly validating business ideas. Based on these beliefs, business modeling assists participants in developing viable business models, whereas effective thinking promotes an adaptive, resource-oriented approach to entrepreneurship. This combination of academic knowledge and practical approaches fosters innovation by leading participants from the early phases of idea development to the difficulties of establishing and scaling a firm.

Methodology: The scouting methodology employed in the Spoke 2 for identifying and nurturing entrepreneurial opportunities is a strategic mix of pull and push approaches. Actively hunting for ideas, the university engages in detailed interviews with researchers, conducts comprehensive mapping of research group efforts, and undertakes desk analysis of its existing portfolio of academic startups and patents. This proactive push approach is complemented by a pull strategy, where the university orchestrates various awareness and capacity-building activities such as courses, workshops, and seminars aimed at fostering an entrepreneurial mindset. Additionally, initiatives like open office hours and open call programs are implemented to encourage the spontaneous emergence of new ideas and ventures. This dual-method approach ensures a thorough and dynamic process of scouting, effectively tapping into both existing and latent entrepreneurial potential within the university community.

Ongoing activities: To find and support innovation inside its ecosystem, Spoke 2 at the University of Trento has started a thorough series of scouting efforts. In order to provide a continuous perspective of

the inventive outputs that are already available as well as possible areas for future development, these operations started with the careful mapping of patents and other Intellectual Resources (IRs). Concurrently, the university began a comprehensive mapping of research groups and main investigators with the goal of identifying both innovation hotspots and strategic research areas where the IP output and valorisation could be improved. This propaedeutic activity enables a tailored approach to foster existing entrepreneurial drivers and to stimulate the emergence of such drivers in underrepresented areas of competence. The university's methods are continually checked to make sure they remain in line with worldwide standards of excellence through this process, which involves benchmarking against national and international best practices. In addition to these strategic objectives, the research group is conducting a detailed literature assessment on scouting tactics in order to improve and develop its methodology. Spoke 2 has initiated a number of programs to increase awareness and develop capacity for entrepreneurial engagement in tandem with these strategic goals. These consist of the Business Design Program, the Business Growth Program, and the Crash Course on Intellectual Property Rights. Furthermore: the School of Innovation (SOI), which is actively attempting to cultivate an innovative and entrepreneurial culture among students and researchers, offers a comprehensive 12 ECTS curriculum in line with these goals.

2.3. SPOKE 2 CC1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

(e.g., conferences, meetings, participation in kick-off and mid-term plenary sessions, overall working group activities, interaction with the stakeholders)

The University of Trento's Spoke 2 team participated in several meetings, focusing on coordination and planning. Regular meetings with administrative staff addressed operational and logistical aspects of the project, ensuring alignment with university procedures. The team also attended sessions with the iNEST CC1 workgroup, discussing approaches to innovation and sharing updates. Meetings with UniTrento Spoke 2 representatives provided a forum for discussing research progress and internal activities. Interaction with Hub Innovazione Trentino (HIT) representatives facilitated connections with the local innovation ecosystem. Additionally, discussions with the Division for Valorization and Impact of Research helped align the various proposed scouting activities with the current operations of the division.. These meetings supported the ongoing development and implementation of Spoke 2's activities.

Selected members of the Spoke 2 group at the University of Trento participated in an event organized by Fondazione Hub Innovazione Trentino, in collaboration with EIT Health. This event focused on showcasing high-tech entrepreneurial ideas and research advancements in health and life sciences from the region, aligning them with the needs of SMEs, healthcare providers, and other key stakeholders in the healthcare sector. The event offered a comprehensive overview of the challenges and opportunities in the intersection of local research and entrepreneurial initiatives with the technological demands of the industry. Through various panel discussions, the Spoke 2 representatives engaged in valuable exchanges with health innovation leaders, delving into the latest trends, best practices, and networking opportunities. This participation was instrumental in highlighting their projects, understanding market needs, and fostering potential collaborations, thereby enhancing the impact and reach of their research and entrepreneurial efforts in the health and life sciences sectors.

On 15/12/2023 the Scouting Specialist participated in the handshake meeting with Scouting Specialists from the other spokes, kicking off the scouting activities for Spoke 2.

2.4. SPOKE 2 CCI MAIN RESULTS

(main results achieved till now, including pictures, photos, graphs, table, link to on-line material, etc...)

Spoke 2 at the University of Trento fulfilled various foundational tasks throughout the early stages of its research operations. The internal research group was formed, laying the groundwork for the project's ongoing research efforts. This step entailed aligning the team members' expertise and aims. There was also the selection and hiring of a scouting specialist and a startup analyst. These positions are critical for directing the project's emphasis on scouting and entrepreneurial development. Interaction with local stakeholders, particularly Hub Innovazione Trentino (HIT) officials, was established. This engagement should make future collaboration within the local innovation ecosystem easier. Regular meetings with both the local and iNEST research groups were organized. The purpose of these sessions is to establish a consistent research methodology and to stimulate joint efforts. Preparations for the 2024 Proof of Concept (POC) program have begun in conjunction with Fondazione Caritro. This program is designed to put research ideas to the test and validate them in real-world contexts. The Crash Course, Business Design, and Business Growth programs were also introduced. These programs, which focus on intellectual property rights, business design, and growth strategies, aim to improve participants' entrepreneurial skills, aligning with the university's goals of encouraging innovation and entrepreneurship."

2.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

(Bullet points and brief summary, administration topics)

Spoke 2 at the University of Trento faced various problems during the project's initial phase. One major concern was the delay in commencing internal budget procedures, which impacted the project's total timeframe. Additionally, the process of finding a scouting specialist took longer than anticipated. The problem in hiring a startup analyst was even more pronounced, with two different recruitment calls failing to provide a viable candidate.

Corrective activities have been planned for 2024 in response to these challenges. Internal budget procedures will be streamlined and expedited to provide a smoother operating flow in the future. Recognizing the necessity of filling the startup analyst position, a fresh and more concentrated recruitment campaign will be launched. This new call will be geared to attract a larger pool of competent candidates while taking into account lessons learnt from prior attempts to ensure a successful recruiting process.

2.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

(With reference to the 2024 activities)

In 2024 the actions of the Spoke 2 will focus on:

Recruitment of a Startup Analyst. As described in section 2.5, a more focused recruitment campaign was launched on 15/01/2024. The Startup Analyst is expected to take service starting on 01/03/2024.

Repository submission of 10 startups. The scouting workflow for the shortlisting of the first battery of startups is being streamlined. The Scouting Specialist is working coordinately with HIT to identify at least 10 entrepreneurial ideas to feed the pre-selection funnel. The selection is focusing on known early

stage initiatives: mature ideas, non-incorporated groups and embryonic stage startups. These shall be further shortlisted on an individual basis based on their need for pre-acceleration and acceleration services. The project repository is expected to be filed by 31/01/2024.

Set-up of a standardized scouting process. The literature research and benchmarking activities mentioned in section 2.2 are being combined with the existing best practices adopted by Spoke 2. This shall include push and pull approaches, combining 1-to-1 in person visits to the research groups with broader awareness-raising approaches such as startup contests, workshops, events, and the execution of system-level communication plans. This approach would increase the pool of entrepreneurial ideas, ideally generating at least 40-50 proposals. These shall then be short-listed in the second battery of 10 startups. This procedure is also expected to generate long-lasting effects in promoting academic entrepreneurship in the ecosystem.

Contribution to setting-up the acceleration activities. To implement the acceleration activities, the Spoke 2 is crafting a strategy that involves coordination with the research units of both the University of Verona (UniVR) and the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano (UniBZ). This collaborative approach includes sharing best practices, insights from literature research, and benchmarking. The strategy encompasses structured mentoring, expert industry access, and investor networking, along with the implementation of acceleration programs for prototype development and market testing, along with training sessions focusing on business scaling and market strategies will be integral. The aim is to guide the selected startups from the pre-acceleration phase to market readiness, facilitating their scaling and investment opportunities.

References

- Blank, S. (2020). *The four steps to the epiphany: successful strategies for products that win*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Blank, S., & Dorf, B. (2020). *The startup owner's manual: The step-by-step guide for building a great company*. John Wiley & Sons.
- De Weck, O. L. (2022). *Technology roadmapping and development: a quantitative approach to the management of technology*. Springer Nature.
- Frederiksen, D. L., & Brem, A. (2017). How do entrepreneurs think they create value? A scientific reflection of Eric Ries' Lean Startup approach. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 13, 169-189.
- Hofer, A. and J. Potter (2010), "Universities, Innovation and Entrepreneurship: Criteria and Examples of Good Practice", OECD Local Economic and Employment Development (LEED) Papers, No. 2010/10, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/5km7rq0pq00q-en>.
- Lombardi, P., & Berk, A. (2022). *Startup program design, A practical guide for creating corporate accelerators and incubators at any organization: A Practical Guide for Creating Accelerators and Incubators at Any Organization*. McGraw-Hill Education.
- Sarasvathy, S. D. (2009). *Effectuation: Elements of entrepreneurial expertise*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

3. SPOKE 3 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1 (6 pages)

Spoke 3, coordinated by the University of Udine, specifically focuses on promoting innovation and creating conditions for green and digital transitions in the advanced manufacturing sector. This goal is further declined into 5 thematic areas, or research topics (RT):

- RT1: Energy
- RT2: Smart manufacturing, Mechatronics and Robotics
- RT3: Materials
- RT4: Artificial Intelligence and Data Science
- RT5: Organizational, economical and legal aspects

In this scientific context, the cross-cutting activity 1 plays an important role in fostering a coordinated and transversal approach across all Spokes within the iNEST project. Aligned with the framework of an innovation ecosystem, this activity serves the purpose of valorizing innovative ideas arising from the research activities of the Spoke 3 and facilitating the generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs.

3.1. SPOKE 3 CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

(title of the task, brief description of the topics, participants, general organisation and planning, expected results)

Being a cross-cutting activity, the objectives are common to all Spokes, regardless of the specific research topics each university is engaged in.

These objectives consist in supporting innovative ideas and facilitating the birth and development of startups and spinoffs.

In particular, as jointly agreed with the coordinator and the Steering Committee of the cross-cutting activity 1, some quantitative objectives have been set for each Spoke. These goals are listed below.

- collection of at least 10 ideas coming from within the Spoke
- selection of at least 8 ideas, through a pre-screening process
- selection of at least 4 ideas, through a screening process, to be supported in the preparation of the pitch to be presented during the Selection Day.

With respect to Sub Task CC1.2.4 - Open Innovation, the main goal is to foster the intersection between the solutions proposed by the academic startups and spinoffs and the innovation needs of the corporate world.

3.2. SPOKE 3 CC1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

A brief summary of the CC1 Tasks is reported below:

- CC1.1: Planning and validation

- **CC1.2: Pre-acceleration**

- Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 9-40
 - Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 10-23
 - Sub Task CC1.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 12-26
 - Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities. The objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners in order to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs and co-innovation activities between universities, startups and companies.
Responsible: UNIUD
Duration: months 9-40
- CC1.3: Acceleration
 - CC1.4: Fundraising

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and pre-acceleration activities in the Spoke "3"

Background / State of the Art: Basing on this activity framework, during the reporting period the main focus has been on a series of pivotal activities crucial for the consolidation and development of ongoing initiatives.

The very first activity was represented by the establishment of the working group of the Spoke. In this regard, the University of Udine engaged in the recruitment process leading to the identification of the roles of the Open Innovation Manager (Enrico Pusceddu) and the Scouting Specialist (Eduardo Canaku). The working group also includes their scientific supervisor (Professor Cinzia Battistella), UNIUD Representative for the Cross Cutting activity CC1 (Professor Piergiorgio Comuzzo), as well as the Delegates of the Rector for the "Third Mission" and for Technology Transfer and the Spin-Off Technical Committee (Professors Monica Anese and Giovanni Cortella). The working group closely cooperates with all the offices supporting the research activities (Technology Transfer, Intellectual Property, Project Planning, Administrative). There is also a strong cooperation with the Spoke's affiliated partners (POLOAA and FINN).

A meticulous review of the project documentation, encompassing deliverables, reports, and project presentations was conducted. This was aimed at understanding the general framework, progress and objectives of the project, and in particular the cross-cutting activity CC1, in order to ensure consistency, completeness, and quality in future actions and documentation. Next, the working group carried out a state-of-the-art survey with respect to strategies and best practices implemented by various universities related to entrepreneurship and open innovation in academic settings. In parallel, we also performed an analysis of articles and publications, to identify the main determining factors facilitating the development of startups in academic settings and promoting open innovation between companies and universities.

Methodology: The previously described research activities provided a fundamental framework to guide future strategies of the Spoke, giving inspiration and valuable insights for our context. The University, together with the affiliated partners, defined a proposal for the actions and activities concerning Spoke 3, according to (i) the material reviewed, (ii) the information gathered thanks to the research conducted and (iii) the inputs from the coordinator of the cross-cutting activity CC1 regarding methods, timings and goals.

This action plan will guide the activities of the Spoke in the coming months, ensuring a systematic and targeted approach. It encompasses various lines of activities with respect to scouting entrepreneurial ideas from academia. The first follows a bottom-up approach and it is represented by an in-house mapping of research projects currently underway at UNIUD to identify those with the highest innovative and entrepreneurial potential. In particular, it consists of 1-on-1 meetings with researchers in which highlight some key elements of their research projects, such as the novelty with respect to the state of the art, the composition team (if present), and any validation activities already carried out. The second activity is related to events and initiatives already organized by the Spoke on the topic of entrepreneurial culture (not necessarily related to the iNEST project). On these occasions, follow-up activities can be conducted, contacting participants to present the iNEST project, intercepting students and researchers already interested in the startup world.

Ongoing activities: After the approval by the coordinator and the Steering Committee of the cross-cutting activity 1, we started to implement the action plan, with particular focus on the mapping of the research projects currently underway at the University. We conducted several meetings with researchers, PhD candidates and research fellows. The interviews focused on various aspects. First, we discussed the “research question” underlying the project, in order to understand the problem that they want to address. Then we moved to the current state of progress of their research projects, concerning in particular any results already achieved, as well as the expected outcomes and the roadmap for the development of the project. Other topics mentioned during the interview were related, for instance, to the potential beneficiaries of the outputs of the project, with the purpose of providing a proxy of the “target customers” of the hypothetical startup, and the novelty compared to the state of the art, for understanding both the degree of disruption and the technical feasibility of the proposed solution. All the information gathered during the interviews allowed us to approximately assess the potential of the research projects in terms of entrepreneurship. Some preliminary results are presented and discussed more detail in section 2.4.

In parallel, we also implemented the activities related to Open Innovation (Sub Task CC1.2.4), in order to boost and facilitate partnerships and joint projects between firms and Universities, as described more in detail in the related report.

3.3. SPOKE 3 CCI DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

(e.g., conferences, meetings, participation in kick-off and mid-term plenary sessions, overall working group activities, interaction with the stakeholders)

During the reporting period, several coordination meetings were convened to facilitate effective communication and ensure optimal synchronization among all the various teams involved in the project. These meetings provided a crucial opportunity for discussing action plans, progress made, assessing emerging challenges, and formulating collaborative strategies to be adopted in the future months. The primary objective of such gatherings was to promote proactive project management, enabling each partner to contribute in an informed and coordinated manner toward the achievement of predetermined objectives.

Some of the most important meetings are listed below.

- On 15th of September 2023, we held a meeting at UNIUD Lab Village for starting the definition of the action plan
- On the 5th of October 2023, an online meeting was convened involving the affiliated partners of Spoke 3 (POLOAA and FINN) in order to share and discuss the first version of the action plan, aligning strategies and coordinating future actions.
- On the 27th of October 2023, in Pordenone, various project partners gathered to present and validate the action plan. This meeting allowed to agree on the future course of action of project partners, the specific goals to achieve and the correspondent timelines
- On the 14th of December 2023, an online meeting was convened, bringing together all scouting specialists involved in the project. Methodologies and tools were shared, ensuring uniformity, harmonized approaches, to facilitate the streamlined implementation across the diverse Spokes.

Moreover, two public events have been organized by UNIUD. They were open to all the academic community and were aimed at raising the awareness of entrepreneurship through talks, speeches and success stories from startups and spin offs coming in the University.

Corresponding posters can be found below.

**UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DI UDINE**
hic sunt futura

**PROGETTO
CONDIVISO**

**Uniid
Lab Village**

TAVOLA ROTONDA

Imprenditorialità e innovazione: dall'Università alla start up

Lunedì 23 ottobre 2023, ore 16
Area Multimodiale SMACT3
Uniid Lab Village
Via Sondrio 2, Udine

ORE 15.45: REGISTRAZIONI

ORE 16: SALUTI INTRODUTTIVI
Giovanni Cortella
Dolagato al Trattamento Tecnologico
Università degli studi di Udine

MODERA
Cinzia Battistella
Docente di Ingegneria Economico-Gestionale
Università degli studi di Udine

PARTECIPANO

Luce Cesena
Stream

Adriano Luci
LOD

Roberto Petrella
Koala Electronics

Marco Sortino
Dynext

Ruben Specogna
EMC Gems

ORE 17.30 INTERVENTO
Agevolazioni per le start up innovative
Giulia Simeoni
Commissione di Studio "Consulenza e
pianificazione fiscale / Contenziosa"

ORE 17.45 DEBATTITO E CONCLUSIONI

SEGUIRÀ APERITIVO

iscrittione entro il 19 ottobre 2023, al link
<https://www.uniid.it/it/servizi/impresa/punto-impresa/iscrittione>

SEGRETERIA ORGANIZZATIVA
Punto Impresa Uniid
www.uniid.it/puntoimpresa
T. 0432 556094
puntoimpresa@uniud.it

www.facebook.com/uniud/
twitter.com/uniud
www.instagram.com/universitaudiudine/
puntoimpresa@uniud.it

**UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DI UDINE**
hic sunt futura

**PROGETTO
CONDIVISO**

TAVOLA ROTONDA

Quali strategie per una start up vincente

Martedì 24 ottobre 2023, ore 14
Aula 1, Polo Economico-giuridico
via Tomadini 30/A, Udine

**ORE 13.45
REGISTRAZIONI**

**ORE 14
SALUTI INTRODUTTIVI**
Marcellino Gaudenzi
Direttore del Dipartimento
di Scienze Economiche e Statistiche
Università degli Studi di Udine

TAVOLA ROTONDA

INTRODUCE E MODERA
Josanco Floreani
Università degli Studi di Udine

PARTECIPANO

Dino Feragotto
Confindustria Udine

Filippo Bianco
TEC4I FVG

Carlo Asquini
Unicorn Trainers Club

Giacomo Pinali
ai4iv

Fabio Bignolini
Northern Lights
Composites

iscrittione entro il 23 ottobre, al link:
<https://www.uniid.it/it/servizi/impresa/punto-impresa/iscrittione-24-10-23>

SEGRETERIA ORGANIZZATIVA
Punto Impresa Uniid
www.uniid.it/puntoimpresa
T. 0432 556094
puntoimpresa@uniud.it

www.facebook.com/uniud/
twitter.com/uniud
www.instagram.com/universitaudiudine/
puntoimpresa@uniud.it

3.4. SPOKE 3 CCI MAIN RESULTS

(main results achieved till now, including pictures, photos, graphs, table, link to on-line material, etc...)

With respect to the pre-acceleration phase, the main results achieved thanks to the previously described activities are presented below. We reached out to 44 researchers, PhD candidates and research fellows, with a response rate of nearly 70%. We also assessed some other projects that the University was already aware of from past experiences. In addition, we assessed some ideas developed during the Winter Hackathon, which took place in early December at UNIUD Lab Village, as part of the Cross Cutting activity CC2.

The potential startupper involved (namely who is conducting the research projects or has a business idea), have different roles within the University, going from students (8), to researchers (20), to PhD Candidates (3), to Research Fellows (6).

We interviewed them, according to the methodology previously described in Section 2.2. The most representative profiles identified are listed below.

1. **Non Entrepreneurial Projects:** they do not present direct entrepreneurial outlets, as their goal is purely scientific or to develop policy recommendations/best practices/etc. This category hardly fits into the purposes of the cross-cutting activity CC1 and cannot be included in the Pre-Acceleration and the Acceleration Program.
2. **Early Stage Projects:** they show entrepreneurial potential but still require testing and analysis of results to validate the proposed solution. These projects may be promising and could fall under the second cycle of the Pre-acceleration and Acceleration programs that will be implemented in the next months.
3. **Potential Entrepreneurial Projects:** they present entrepreneurial potential, but the researcher shows poor interest in embarking on an entrepreneurial path. These projects might be interesting for the purposes of the cross-cutting activity and could be included in the Pre-Acceleration and Acceleration programs if the researchers will be properly convinced, by uncovering entrepreneurial potential.
4. **Engageable Entrepreneurial Projects:** they display entrepreneurial potential and the researcher is open to the possibility of embarking on an entrepreneurial pathway. These projects are completely in line with the purposes of the cross-cutting activity and most likely will be included in the Pre-Acceleration and Acceleration programs.

The following graph summarizes a preliminary characterization of the analyzed projects.

In addition, with respect to Sub Task CC1.2.4 - Open Innovation, the actions carried out during the reference period resulted in Identification of innovation performance indicators for the selection of companies to be involved in Open Innovation activities. Starting from these indicators, a first mapping of innovation-oriented companies has been done. A more detailed discussion can be found in the correspondent report.

3.5. **ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN** (half page)

(Bullet points and brief summary, administration topics)

During the reference period, no significant delays and administrative concerns have been registered. However, some issues have emerged regarding the preparation of participants in pre-acceleration and acceleration programs. These issues lie mainly in the difference between the scientific research approach and the entrepreneurship approach. To address these issues, the Spoke planned more activities in order spread the startup mindset and raise awareness with respect to innovation and entrepreneurship.

3.6. **NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES** (half page)

(With reference to the 2024 activities)

In 2024, Spoke 3 aims at the implementation of more structured activities with the goal of fostering and enhancing the entrepreneurial culture within the academic community. These initiatives are strategically designed to better equip participants for the upcoming second cycle envisioned by the project, facilitating a more effective and informed engagement of participants in the Pre-Acceleration and Acceleration program.

4. SPOKE 4 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1 (6 pages)

The main objective of Spoke 4 is to ally all the stakeholders participating in the built environment transformation to overcome the current challenges together with the adaptation to social, economic and climate changes. Hence, the Spoke has the chance of becoming the node connecting all the sub-systems of the territorial transformation, promoting a collaborative and synergistic network between all the supply chain and sector operators: academic research, design practice, manufacturing, construction, commerce and distribution, the credit system, and public administrations.

- **RT1 - Strategic plan for the development of the construction and sustainable design sectors.** RT1 developed an analysis of the built environment while maintaining a transcale approach. RT1 identified the main sustainability objectives for the following building phase in Italy, the first to transform the built environment non-expansively;
- **RT2 - Technological solutions for the construction and sustainable design sectors,** RT2 identified an innovative method for selecting the survey areas according to the most sensitive territory for each topic and tested the technique in eleven different sites;
- **RT3 - Interaction between environments and human beings in the construction and sustainable design sectors.** In the first year, it aimed to identify the most critical issues regarding collective and individual well-being. The first year acted as a pivot in managing relations between general studies in the Northeast;

In this scientific context, the **cross-cutting activity 1** keep an important role in fostering entrepreneurship education and dissemination within university ecosystems, connecting the business world with the scientific community in order to create a collaborative network to be maintained over time.

One of the goals is to integrate research institutes to interact with the regional context, with the ultimate goal of contributing to the creation of a market economy, through continuous trades and synergistic interactions.

4.1. SPOKE 4 CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITY 1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

(title of the tasks, brief description of the topics, participants, general organisation and planning, expected results)

iNEST tasks' can be described as follows:

- **CC1.1: Planning and validation:** planning was completed in March 2023. Validation and periodical reviews are ongoing till the end of the project.
- **CC1.2: Pre-Acceleration:** ongoing (first Pre-Acceleration round: November 2023 - March 2024)
- **CC1.3: Acceleration:** first development of the Acceleration Framework and engagement and coordination of the Key Actors; the implementation of the Acceleration phase will start at the end of the first Pre-Acceleration round (task leader: UniVR)
- **CC1.4: Fundraising:** yet not started (task leader: UniTS)

The objectives of Task **CC1.1** were concluded by outlining common actions for all participating spokes. A common strategy was provided for all 9 spokes, planned through scheduled meetings and constant communication through online data sharing platforms.

Regarding the activities of Luav University, it was decided to be able to start the scouting activities (CC1.2) in November, in order to get inside the design laboratories, starting a scouting activity involving students, researchers and selecting early stage start-ups born within the entrepreneurship training program.

Ten projects were selected, following interviews with startupper and review of business plans and videopitch. The main information (proposer data, brief description of the business idea, relevant entity) was shared with the 9 spoke and collected within a Drive file.

Scouting activities were carried out by specialized staff on duty at the University's TTO pending the recruitment of the dedicated figures. The startupper will be accompanied by the scouting specialists to the selection phase, refining and integrating the materials that will be displayed during the selection day.

4.2. SPOKE 4 CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITY 1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

List of CC1 Tasks:

- CC1.1: Planning and validation
- CC1.2: Pre-acceleration
 - Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 9-40
 - Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 10-23
 - Sub Task CC1.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 12-26
 - Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities. the objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners in order to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs and co-innovation activities between universities, startups and companies.
Responsible: UNIUD
Duration: months 9-40
- CC1.3: Acceleration
- CC1.4: Fundraising

Focus on Task CCI.2: Scouting and pre-acceleration activities in the Spoke 4

Background / State of the Art:

Since 2017, every year Iuav has organized a training and idea-acceleration program aimed at students, alumni, PhD students, researchers and collaborators.

The goal is to enhance ideas born within undergraduate, doctoral or master's workshops, with high business potential and/or elevated technological value and innovative value, and to turn them into academic spinoffs.

The program is structured in two phases:

1. Startup School - training course on entrepreneurship

The training activity is aimed at entrepreneurial alphabetization through the analysis of successful cases, good practices and opportunities emerging from society. The focus is on assessing the impact of the idea on the context and the importance of the team for the technical and economic sustainability of the project. Startup school is organized, with open meetings for everyone to attend. Course attendance allows students to earn university credits and LinkedIn badges.

Classes are held in-person and online and involve expert teachers in the field of business and startups. Face-to-face training sessions are alternated with workshop sessions for analysis and development of ideas, encouraging cross-fertilization among participants. CEOs of experienced and successful startups are also invited to bring their experience and feedback

2. Start.Hub - ideas acceleration program

A maximum of 12/14 teams, formed/consolidated during the Startup School training period, will access the second part of the program. Every team must meet specific criteria: have an innovative idea, the team must consist of at least two members and one of them must be affiliated (in the present or the past) with IUAV.

The course includes project work days, divided into groups and supported by a mentor who follows all stages of project development. The last meeting is structured as an intensive residential workshop, alternating face-to-face didactic activities, group analytical work, and one-on-one meetings with experts in marketing, business, administration, IT, user experience, product, patent, legal, etc.

At the end of the course, there is a pitch competition in which teams present their ideas and prototypes to an audience of investors, institutions and companies that decide the five winners who are awarded a cash prize to invest in the business idea.

Methodology:

Start.Hub, the idea pre-acceleration program by which luav historically selects, trains and accelerates ideas born within the university, becomes the pool from which to select the best startup ideas to carry into the Entrepreneurial training program (CC1.2.3).

This year luav proposes 10 ideas/startups coming out of the 2022 and 2023 strat.hub programs. For next year, the best startups will be selected to participate in the 2024 pathway, which will start in March 2024 and end in June 2024

A series of actions to disseminate the initiative on the Inest ecosystem and Start.Hub initiative have been established. A laboratory was set, the "Start.Hub LAB," a physical space within the luav venues that aims to serve as a stable office for meeting interested target audiences about the initiative. In addition to receiving constant online support, our startupper and future startupper are allowed to take advantage of a space that serves as an exchanger of ideas and discussion between scouting specialists, students and interested parties. The team has scheduled a series of meetings to present the initiative within the bachelor's, master's and doctoral school to engage professors and students in the initiative.

Until the scouting specialist is selected, the luav University technology transfer office team has been coordinating the preparatory work. The team has been coordinating with luav assignees and researchers from spoke4 and the CC1 operations group.

Ongoing activities:

Nov '23 > Mar '24 - Start.Hub LAB and one-to-one meetings with startupper

Dec '23 > Mar '24 - Expression of interest for the Start.Hub 2024 program

Dec '23 > Jan '24 - Selection call for scouting specialist

4.3. SPOKE 4 CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITY 1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

To strengthen scouting activities and the dissemination of activities, specific interventions have been planned within the design laboratories of the IUAV University. The interventions had the objective of disseminating what the Start Hub 2023 path was and what the activities that can be undertaken at the end of it will be. To make up for the lack of the iNEST scouting specialist, the activities were carried out by the TTO Service, in particular in the figure of the Technologist and research fellows.

Traditional engagement techniques were chosen for scouting: one-on-one meetings, events with the doctoral school to raise awareness of PhDs, PhD students and research fellows, events and dissemination in classrooms.

- **29 NOV 2023, WES 09:00 – 16:00**
iNEST Spoke 4 kick off meetings with scholars, partners and affiliates
Venue: Ca' Tron Palace Iuav University of Venice
 The purpose of the meeting was to present the project and to start the working tables around the different topics: landscape and building supply chain trends in the Northeast; real estate market in the Northeast; building technologies characterizing
- **5 DEC 2023, TUE 14:00 – 16:00**
Dissemination Activities
Venue: online
 Presentation activity of the iNEST pre-acceleration path for the selected Start Up and awareness raising for participation in the Cross-Cutting activity #1
- **7 DEC 2023, THU 14:30 – 16:00**
Dissemination Activities
Venue: Cotonificio, Iuav University of Venice
 Dissemination activities of the Start Hub path, presentation of the iNEST pre-acceleration path and awareness raising on entrepreneurship issues held within the Civic Space Design Laboratory, Prof. Fagnoni
- **12 DEC 2023, TUE 14:30 – 16:00**
Dissemination Activities
Venue: Cotonificio, Iuav University of Venice
 Dissemination activities of the Start Hub path, presentation of the iNEST pre-acceleration path and awareness raising on entrepreneurship issues held within the Design Criticism Laboratory, Prof. Bassi
- **13 DEC 2023, WES 09:00 – 16:00**
iNEST Spoke 4 kick off meetings with scholars, partners and affiliates

Venue: Ca' Tron Palace Iuav University of Venice

The purpose of the meeting was to present the project and to start the working tables around the different topics: landscape and building supply chain trends in the Northeast; real estate market in the Northeast; building technologies characterizing.

- **10 GEN 2024, TUE 09:30 – 11:00**

Dissemination Activities

Venue: Cotonificio, Iuav University of Venice

Dissemination activities of the Start Hub path, presentation of the iNEST pre-acceleration path and awareness raising on entrepreneurship issues held within the Iuav Doctoral School.

- **11 GEN 2024, WES 14:30 – 16:00**

Dissemination Activities

Venue: Cotonificio, Iuav University of Venice

Dissemination activities of the Start Hub path, presentation of the iNEST pre-acceleration path and awareness raising on entrepreneurship issues held within the Design Laboratory for Urban Innovation, Prof. Micelli, Ostanel, Munarin.

4.4. SPOKE 4 CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITY 1 MAIN RESULTS

Through pre-screening activities, Iuav selected 10 startups to apply to the accelerator program. Below the list of ideas/startups as detailed in the [Pre-Screening repository](#).

- HAM Benefit
- RI-PRESE
- RE-HUB
- FARMA 282
- Elemento
- Selvatica
- Argo
- Tiny House
- Horizon
- Take It

In-depth documentation is attached to this report (section 3 - references).

The selection procedure by comparative evaluation for the selection of the scouting specialist has been published on December 15, 2023 and ended on January 19, 2024. Publication of the results is scheduled starting from January 26, 2024.

Link to the public notice: <https://www.iuav.it/Lavora-con/assegnin/assegnin/archivio/2023/rep--508-2/Allegato-1-rettore.pdf>

4.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

A delay was encountered in the recruitment of the scouting specialist. Despite the delay in recruiting this figure, the TTO managed to make up for it by hiring a unit already in place at the service and carry out the activities as required. To date, the call for recruiting the figure is in the process of closing and is expected to be in place within 40 days.

The scouting approaches, previously explained, differed among the universities, with those chosen by Iuav University in particular coming into synergy with internal initiatives led by Technology Transfer and Intellectual Property Enhancement.

The scouting specialist selected 10 start-ups to participate in the iNEST Cross-Cutting activity call #1 seeks diverse, interdisciplinary teams working on challenging ideas.

The start-ups were selected from the most viable business ideas within our university. The proposed entrepreneurial ideas were born within the Strat Hub training track and followed a six-month training course. The same scouting activity is planned for next year.

4.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

The scouting actions to be undertaken for next year will be the same as those applied for the year 2023/2024: one-to-one meetings with start-ups born within the Start Hub pathway, dissemination in classrooms for greater awareness towards students, and kick-off meetings with the iNEST working team to assess the progress of the project on a fortnightly basis.

To allow for greater contamination of ideas and the construction of project proposals that are competitive in the Triveneto and national territory, it was decided to open the Start Hub call also to students who belong to the universities of the iNEST consortium. The requirement for participation in the internal competition remains, however, to have at least one luav component within the proposing group. The same line of selection applied this year will be followed for next year.

The scouting specialist will have the task of selecting the most viable ideas within the University and accompanying them throughout the iNEST pre-acceleration process.

5. SPOKE 5 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1 (6 pages)

The research activities of Spoke 5 address current issues related to **Smart and sustainable environments (manufacturing, working, living)**.

These are supported and enhanced by four Research Topics (RTs), namely:

- **RT1 - New and Emerging Technologies for Human Centric Manufacturing and other industrial working environment**
- **RT2 - Digital Twin in Industries 5.0**
- **RT3 - People, organization, and processes for Industry 5.0**
- **RT4 - Personalized Assistive Technologies and Smart Environments for Inclusive Living in private and public spaces**

Within this framework, the **cross-cutting activity 1** is relevant to support the development of new business ideas from research through a coordinated and transversal approach across all Spokes within the iNEST project. Aligned with the framework of an innovation ecosystem, the cross-cutting activity 1 is oriented to sustain the identification and valorization of innovative ideas arising from the research activities of the Spoke 5 connected to the relationship between digitalization and sustainability in different environments, by facilitating the generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs.

5.1. SPOKE 5 CCI OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

(title of the task, brief description of the topics, participants, general organisation and planning, expected results)

Objectives and key results

The Spoke's shared goal is the development of innovative, smart, sustainable, digitally-driven working and living environments within a human-centric design framework.

In this respect, the CCI objective is to identify and develop innovative ideas related to the different research topics connected with the focus of Spoke 5, specifically related to the nexus between physical and digital worlds, shaped by digitalization and new technological tools and where social sustainability ("human-centered" manufacturing and living environments) is concerned.

This is a wide area of research that can generate business ideas from different research streams, such as those related to technological trajectories and data collection and exploitation in an Industry 5.0 perspectives; new applications in the human-machine interface; context of innovative (smart, sustainable) environments, and many more potentially scoutable.

The cross-cutting activity 1 aims specifically to contribute to the innovation ecosystem promoting the scouting of innovative ideas connected of the past and current research of the different actors involved in the Spoke 5 in order to select most promising ones for the acceleration activities and funding opportunity.

Objectives also refer also to:

- increasing the awareness of researchers of potential business applications of research results to new entrepreneurial activities promoted by researchers and test them in multiple forms (business model generations, proof-of-concept)
- enhancing the possibility to launch spin-offs rooted on academic research to continue the exploitation of relationship between research and innovation and business applications
- favoring the exploitation of research results (e.g. patents) existing at the Spoke 5 level converting them into new start-ups and spin-offs

5.2. SPOKE 5 CC1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

List of CC1 Tasks:

- CC1.1: Planning and validation
- **CC1.2: Pre-acceleration**
 - Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 9-40
 - Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 10-23
 - Sub Task CC1.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 12-26
 - Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities. the objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners in order to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs and co-innovation activities between universities, startups and companies.
Responsible: UNIUD
Duration: months 9-40
- CC1.3: Acceleration
- CC1.4: Fundraising

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and pre-acceleration activities in the Spoke "5"

Background / State of the Art:

- Structured set of activities at the University (Spoke 5 coordinator) level related to the support of spin-off development and engagement for growth
- Established initiatives for entrepreneurial development targeting researchers and students
- Partnership and collaboration with key actors at the national level for technological transfer and spin-off generations
- Experience in innovative training

Methodology:

- Partner selection for design of event planning and implementation focused on explaining how to valorize knowledge and research into business
- Survey /questionnaire for satisfaction analysis and level of engagement of researchers to be spread to participants of events for follow-up for scouting activities
- Analysis/comparison of different knowledge and competences required to support business development (in the context of Spoke 5)

Ongoing activities:

- Development of activity plan related to the scouting activities
- Identification of targets to be involved for idea collection and considered to be involved in the scouting activity (analysis and selection)
- Coordination with the CC1 scientific group for alignment in terms of selection process and profiles of the ideas and entrepreneurs-to-be
- Program of online meetings targeting researchers to increase awareness of research application for business creation and valorization of research in a market context through new firms (spin-offs)
- Selection of 2 scouting specialists
- Outline definition and planning of online training programs focused on start-up and spin-off development

5.3. SPOKE 5 CC1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

(e.g., conferences, meetings, participation in kick-off and mid-term plenary sessions, overall working group activities, interaction with the stakeholders)

Collaborative activities refer to participation of the working group to recurrent meetings organized at the Spoke level to update Spoke 5 members of the current activities as well as at the CC1 level for coordination (scientific coordination) and in relation to scouting activities.

5.4. SPOKE 5 CC1 MAIN RESULTS

(main results achieved till now, including pictures, photos, graphs, table, link to on-line material, etc...)

Main results obtained:

- Awareness of the potentialities related to entrepreneurial dynamics related to research activities by researchers and students
- Awareness related to the creation of spin-offs by professors and research fellows and its potential impacts of the research in the market
- Involvement of researchers in engaging activities to experience how to generate new ideas from research to business and how to start business development

Flyer and pictures of the event organized by University of Padova – November 29th, 2023 (Padova)
“From research to impact: tools and techniques for entrepreneurial development”

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DI PADOVA

WORKSHOP

**Dalla ricerca all'impatto:
strumenti e tecniche per la valorizzazione
imprenditoriale**

29 novembre 2023 ore 9.00
Salone del Palazzo Maldura

ore 9.00 La creazione, la crescita delle imprese spin-off della ricerca pubblica: tools, Lean Canvas e strumenti per il working group	ore 14.00 Working group
ore 13.00 Lunch break	ore 17.30 Restituzione dei risultati

i NEST Interconnected
Nord-Est Innovation
Ecosystem

unipd.it/terza-missione

5.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

(Bullet points and brief summary, administration topics)

- Definition of the profile of scouting specialists to be identified taking into account the different areas of research related to the research domain of Spoke 5 that delayed the selection process. Corrective action taken refer to discussing within the Spoke 5 coordination team and by creating a diversified team that specifically follow CCI for input

5.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

(With reference to the 2024 activities)

Next steps will include the following activities:

- Promote a specific “Call for ideas” within the University of Padova focused on researchers and students participating in events organized to promote entrepreneurship and spin-off initiatives organized during 2023
- Develop scouting activities focused on one-to-one meetings with researchers / inventors (of patents)
- Selection of at least 10 business ideas / start-ups to be involved in the acceleration phase
- Coordination with CCI team at the ecosystem level for outline and manage the selection day.

Main challenges

- Real engagement of researchers with business ideas / start-ups in the early stage available for be involved in the acceleration phase

6. SPOKE 6 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1 (6 pages)

Spoke 6 is centred on conducting research in the fields of tourism, culture, and creative production and translating the results into practical outputs through the implementation of prototypes, experiments, and innovative initiatives. The incubation and acceleration programs within this framework are intended to support and foster entrepreneurial ideas in the domains of tourism, culture, and creativity. These initiatives are further enhanced by four distinct Research Topics (RTs):

- **RT 1 - New Digital Technologies**

These lines promote the development of innovative projects that combine knowledge of the tourism and cultural domain with the adoption of new digital technologies. These include artificial intelligence, blockchain and NFT, IoT and mobile sensing, and virtual and augmented reality, which will serve as a reference for projects to be implemented in the following macro-environments;

- **RT 2 - Data analysis**

These converge on the analysis of big data in tourism and culture from heterogeneous sources. The aim is thus to develop tools to support public policies and more sustainable destination management & marketing strategies. The lines of research may take the form of projects to be implemented in different fields;

- **RT 3 - Sustainable business models**

RT3 research lines aim to transform the business models of tourism, cultural and creative enterprises, organisations, and ecosystems into sustainable ones.

- **RT 4 - New narratives and communication strategies**

The RT4 research lines aim to develop new narrative tools to overcome the stereotypes of tourist destinations and to reconfigure communication in terms of inclusiveness and sustainability.

Spoke 6, led by Ca' Foscari University in collaboration with the Universities of Verona, Trento, and Bolzano, is strategically placed with the ultimate objective of building a strong tourism ecosystem. This ecosystem is distinguished by the seamless interplay of culture and creativity, bolstered by advanced digital and data analysis technologies.

The initiative encompasses four distinct research areas, each carefully designed to illuminate and explore the intricate interdependencies between seemingly disparate phenomena that are, nonetheless, interconnected by the overarching tourism phenomenon.

These research areas serve as focal points for in-depth exploration, allowing us to delve into the complex relationships and interactions within the tourism ecosystem, thereby contributing to a comprehensive understanding of its dynamics.

The ultimate objective is to leverage these insights to foster innovation, sustainable practices, and transformative initiatives within tourism, culture, and creative production.

In this scientific framework, the key role of cross-cutting activity 1 becomes evident as it strives to promote a unified and interdisciplinary approach across all spokes within the iNEST project. Aligned with the principles of an innovation ecosystem, this activity is geared towards enhancing the value of innovative ideas originating from the research endeavours of Spoke 6. Its primary function is to facilitate the generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs.

In the initial phase of our research, we laid the foundation by conducting a thorough analysis of the current situation within the university context. Our analysis honed in on CLab, PiNK, and Associations of Students, while also taking stock of the various student associations within the university. These student-led associations play a vital role in contributing to the university's vibrant academic and social community.

By examining these elements, the research aimed to understand the existing infrastructure, support systems, and collaborative networks within the university, laying the groundwork for subsequent phases of the research project.

To date, only two in-person events have been held with the possibility of remote connection and thus directly reached about one hundred interested people. We have recorded the presentation meeting and are disseminating it to reach a wider audience.

Based on the unique characteristics of the Spoke 6 theme and the surrounding territory, it is likely that individuals can generate innovative ideas and startups related to this theme beyond the academic setting. The area's abundant creativity and deep connection to the region contribute to this potential. As a result, a substantial portion of our research efforts has been focused on carefully analysing the territorial context and devising effective communication strategies to engage with our target audience.

2.1. SPOKE 6 CCI OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW (2 of 6 pages)

(title of the task, brief description of the topics, participants, general organisation and planning, expected results)

Here we focus on the contribution of the Spoke 6 to the **Task CCI.2, "Pre-acceleration"** (see the following Subsection).

The objectives and expected results are summarised in the following table:

Objective	Expected results
O1. increasing the knowledge (strategies, practices, methodologies, tools, ...) on innovation ecosystems to guide the design and implementation of a scouting system for iNEST	A collection of literature references useful for the iNEST scouting system
	A collection of benchmarks, best practices, methodologies, and adaptable reference cases for the Spoke 6 ecosystem.
O2. collaborating on the design of a scouting system for Ca' Foscari University in	A stakeholder engagement strategy tailored to the Spoke 6 peculiarities

Objective	Expected results
Venice within iNEST (defining and personalizing strategies, practices, methodologies and tools to accommodate Spoke 6 specificities)	A tool for collecting and managing applicants information (personal information and details of the ideas, IPs, startups)
	A set of criteria and metrics for the evaluation of the ideas/startups
O3. implementing the scouting system, attracting future entrepreneurs from the University ecosystems and guiding the research efforts towards a proof of concept	A collection of target contacts and the nurturing of the relationships
	Preparatory events and targeted meetings to engage the targets (students, researchers, early stage startups in relation with the Spoke) and to bring the scouting phase to life
	A collection of minimum 10 project ideas / IPs viable in the market/startups to guide through the selection process

The implementation of the scouting system (O3) is planned to be conducted twice and for each round, the expected result is to collect a minimum of 10 ideas/startups that will enter the selection process.

Participants: the Spoke has selected 1 Scouting Specialist - Viviana Carlet, who works under the guidance of the Scouting Officer for the cross-cutting aspects and under the guidance of the Spoke 6 CC1 Committee Member for what concerns the vertical aspects (Tourism, Culture and Creative Industries).

Planning

- O1. Increasing knowledge on innovation ecosystems: from October 2023 to January 2024
- O2. Collaborating with the design of the scouting system: from October 2023 to January 2024
- O3. Implementation of the scouting system - 1st round: from October 2023 to March 2024

Furthermore, the Spoke 6 will collaborate with the CC1 partners on the implementation of the tasks that follow the pre-acceleration phase, namely Task CC1.3 - Acceleration - and Task CC1.4 - Fundraising, which are of fundamental importance for the achievement of the overall goals of the CC1 program.

2.2. SPOKE 6 CC1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES (3 of 6 pages)

List of CC1 Tasks:

- CC1.1: Planning and validation
- **CC1.2: Pre-acceleration**

- Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase. Responsible: UNIVE. Duration: months 9-40
- Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept. Responsible: UNIVE. Duration: months 10-23
- Sub Task CC1.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem. Responsible: UNIVE. Duration: months 12-26
- Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities. This task aims to establish relationships with companies and other partners to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs and co-innovation activities between universities, startups and companies. Responsible: UNIUD. Duration: months 9-40
 - CC1.3: Acceleration
 - CC1.4: Fundraising

List of Spoke "6" RTs

- RT1 New Digital Technologies
- RT2 Data Analytics
- RT3 Sustainable Business Models
- RT4 New Narratives and Communication Strategies

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and pre-acceleration activities in the Spoke "6"

Background / State of the Art:

Existing Offices and Startup Support Initiatives in Ca' Foscari.

Ca' Foscari currently hosts various offices and initiatives dedicated to supporting startups. These include but are not limited to:

. **CLab** (Ca' Foscari Laboratori di Didattica Attiva): Educational laboratories organized around thematic areas in collaboration with partners, emphasizing hands-on learning experiences.

. **PlnK** (Promozione dell'Innovazione e del Know-how): An Innovation and Know-how Promotion portal fostering technological transfer and knowledge exchange between university research and the local community.

. **Student Associations:** Students-led associations contribute to the university community's vibrant academic and social life.

Research Findings on Innovation Ecosystems:

A review of relevant literature and best practices in innovation ecosystems highlights the key elements contributing to successful environments for startups. This includes collaborative networks, access to funding, mentorship programs, and supportive infrastructure.

Research Findings on Innovation Trends in Spoke 6 RTs:

The investigation into innovation trends within the Research Topics (RTs) of Spoke 6 involves exploring how new digital technologies, data analysis, sustainable business models, and new narratives are shaping the fields of tourism, culture, and creative production. This includes an analysis of global best practices and emerging patterns in these areas.

These insights serve as the foundation for understanding the existing startup landscape at Ca' Foscari, drawing on both internal resources and external research to inform the development of strategies and initiatives within the Spoke 6 framework.

Methodology:

Engagement Strategy:

The engagement strategy of Spoke 6 is multifaceted, employing various activities to attract, identify, and engage potential innovators. Key components include:

- Open Call: A widely promoted invitation for innovators, startups, and creative minds to participate.
- Events: Hosting events, workshops, and informational sessions to create awareness and facilitate interaction.
- Targeted Meetings: Engaging in targeted meetings with relevant stakeholders, potential collaborators, and those interested in the intersection of tourism, culture, and creative production.

Selection Process:

The selection process is designed to be thorough and inclusive, ensuring the identification of promising initiatives. The process comprises several stages:

- Open Call Submission: Applicants submit their proposals through a decentralized "Call" Google Form.
- Pre-screening: Applications undergo an initial review, with relevant information stored in a shared repository for collaborative evaluation.
- Selection Form with Pitch Deck: Shortlisted candidates are required to complete a centralized Selection Form, accompanied by a standard Pitch Deck template.
- Screening: Comprehensive screening of applications by the Spoke 6 team, considering innovation, feasibility, and alignment with RTs.
- 1:1 Meetings and Feedback: Selected candidates engage in one-on-one meetings with the Spoke 6 team for deeper discussions and feedback.
- Selection Day: A culminating event where finalists present their projects to a broader audience and a panel of experts for final selection.

Tools:

To facilitate this methodology, the following tools are employed:

- Decentralized "Call" Google Form: An accessible and user-friendly form for open submissions.
- Shared Pre-screening Repository: A collaborative platform for storing and reviewing pre-screening information.
- Centralized Selection Form: A standardized form for shortlisted candidates, ensuring consistency in data collection.
- Standard Pitch Deck Template: A predefined template to guide applicants in presenting key aspects of their projects effectively.

This methodology ensures a fair, transparent, and efficient process for identifying and supporting innovative projects within the Spoke 6 framework of iNest.

Ongoing activities:

- stakeholder engagement: Online open call to collect the submissions, events, targeted meetings, meeting with local activators and active actors working with creative young people and startups;
- pre-screening of the received applications (“yes” / “no” feedback to the Call's applicants) and guiding applicants towards the following stages of the pre-acceleration program;
- one-to-one meetings with interested and interesting people and targets;
- collaborating on the selection and preparation of learning materials for the online Entrepreneurial training (tuition)

2.3. SPOKE 6 CCI DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES (6 of 6 pages)

(e.g., conferences, meetings, participation in kick-off and mid-term plenary sessions, overall working group activities, interaction with the stakeholders)

Events: presentations of the CCI acceleration program: introduction to the iNEST ecosystem structure and actors; illustration of the selection process; launch of the Call

- December 6, 2023, at Campus Scientifico - Mestre, Venice, with Prof. Carlo Bagnoli Coordinator CCI and Prof. Andrea Marella, Scouting Officer - iNEST.
- January 12, 2024, at Ca' Bottacin - Venice, with Prof. Fabrizio Panozzo, Coordinator Spoke 6, Dr. Andrea Marella, Scouting Officer CCI, Prof. Carlo Bagnoli, Coordinator Cross-cutting Activity CCI, and Prof. Maria Lusiani, Member of Committee CCI.

Targeted meetings: meetings with CLab, MIT DesignX Venice, PlnK,...

Participation in stakeholder meetings/events:

- CLab EcoArte (15th December 2023)
- “Call for ideas” events organised by the other Spokes (UniTS and Polo Alto Adriatico in Pordenone, 8th November 2023; SISSA in Trieste, 17th January 2024)
- VeniSIA Innovation Camp (14th and 15th November 2023)
- PlnK + Mosaico workshops on IP and technology transfer and entrepreneurship (November 23)
- Visits to the ecosystems of Politecnico di Torino (October 2023) and Paris Saclay (December 23)

Other dissemination activities: direct emails to a list of “gatekeeper” professors in each of Ca' Foscari's Departments; Ca' Foscari agenda webpage, social media pages (IG, LinkedIn, ...), news on Consorzio iNEST website, university newsletters, creation of a database con personal defined contacts.

2.4. SPOKE 6 CCI MAIN RESULTS (6 of 6 pages)

(main results achieved till now, including pictures, photos, graphs, table, link to online material, etc....)

Focusing on the **Task CCI.2, “Pre-acceleration”**, the main results achieved by the Spoke 6 are:

- the stakeholders' engagement strategy has been defined, customised according to Spoke 6 peculiarities and tested in the first implementation of the system
- a scouting system has been designed (process and tools) and customised according to Spoke 6 peculiarities
- all the tools have been set up and are running in the first implementation of the system
- number of collected target contacts: 100

- number of events: 2
- number of applications to the Call for ideas: 20
- number of Spoke 6 ideas/startups in the pre-screening repository: 20

2.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN (half page)

Addressing challenges head-on, the Spoke 6 team navigated through difficulties to refine the scouting system and boost engagement. Here's a snapshot of encountered problems and the strategic corrective actions implemented:

- Problem: Difficulties in establishing a common framework for all 9 Spokes, specifically a standardised scouting system tailored to iNEST CCI while allowing room for personalisation to accommodate Spoke-specific nuances ⇒ Corrective Action: Intensified interaction with internal stakeholders, orchestrating multiple meetings with iNEST CCI coordinators to collaboratively devise a solution that aligns with the distinct needs of each Spoke while avoiding overlap with internal University initiatives.
- Problem: Initial low attraction of target groups, including students, researchers, and startup enthusiasts ⇒ Corrective Action: Implemented enhanced activation and utilisation of communication channels, leveraging the reach and influence of Consorzio, Spoke 6, and Ca' Foscari University to amplify visibility and engagement among the target audience.

In the face of these challenges, proactive measures and strategic interventions have been instrumental in fortifying the foundations of Spoke 6 and ensuring its resonance within the broader iNEST ecosystem.

Administration topics:

Regarding administrative tasks on CCI, Ca' Foscari University had to deal with the following issues:

- Recruitment of new research fellows in cross-cutting activities
- Budget management

2.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES (half page)

Concerning the 2024 activities, the following steps and challenges lie ahead:

- 15th January 2024, Ca' Bottacin - seminar: "Venice, Tourism, Culture, and Creative Industries: an Innovation Ecosystem. The Initial Results of Ca' Foscari's Research"
- to complete the first pre-acceleration round by the beginning of March 2024
- to collaborate on the connection of the Pre-Acceleration stage to the Acceleration stage (March-April 2024)
- to review the first work round and gain insights for improving the scouting system in the second round

As we embark on these forthcoming activities, the Spoke 6 team remains dedicated to fostering an environment conducive to innovation, collaboration, and sustainable growth within the evolving landscape of tourism, culture, and creative industries.

References

The literature serves as a rich source of stimuli to construct a framework related to the Spoke's themes. Gathering data, insights, and diverse perspectives is crucial to gaining a comprehensive understanding and providing necessary support to the project itself, involving all relevant stakeholders.

Tom Kelley and David Kelley "[Creative Confidence](#)"

Harriet Kelsall "[The Creative's Guide to Starting a Business](#)"

Lisa Congdon "[Art, Inc.: The Essential Guide for Building Your Career as an Artist](#)"

Keith Granet "[The Business of Creativity: How to Build the Right Team for Success](#)"

7. SPOKE 7 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1

The research activities of Spoke 7 address current issues in the sector of smart agri-food. These are supported and enhanced by four Research Topics (RTs), namely:

- RT1 - Business models for a sustainable agri-food
- RT2 - Process and product innovation for a sustainable agri-food
- RT3 - Circular economy

- RT4 - Logistics, supply chain and vertical coordination

In this scientific context, Cross-Cutting Activity 1 plays an important role in fostering a coordinated and transversal approach across all Spokes within the iNEST project. Aligned with the framework of an innovation ecosystem, this activity serves the purpose of valorizing innovative ideas arising from the research activities of Spoke 7 and facilitating the generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs.

7.1. SPOKE 7 CCI OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

(title of the task, brief description of the topics, participants, general organisation and planning, expected results)

The research activities of Spoke7 are focused on advancing research and facilitating technology transfer within the field of smart agri-food. The convergence of digital and green transformations necessitates a comprehensive strategy for agri-food systems, wherein intelligent solutions are cultivated across various domains such as business administration, production (including primary production and industrial processing), circular economy, logistics, and supply chain management. Multiple food value chains within the Nord-Est territory (including grape and wine, olive oil, dairy, baked goods, crops, food and feed, fisheries, and aquaculture) will be addressed through diverse dimensions of potential digital and green innovations. These aims are supported and enhanced by four Research Topics (RTs), namely:

- RT1 Business models for sustainable agri-food at different levels, these activities will focus on the analysis of sustainable business models and sustainability performance in agri-food businesses and of consumer response to corporate social responsibility practices. Through a twin transition on agri-food business models and value chains, the output will be the elaboration of diagnostic and analytic tools measure gaps and identify transitions in business models at the firm and value chain level.
- RT2 Process/product innovation for sustainable agri-food. The activities will be focused on the Development of innovative systems, based on real time processing of sensor data using process-based, AI and data-driven approaches, for improving crop and food production processes, finished products quality, and packaging. This will exploit also the use of extracts, bio-resources, bio-molecules and digital databases for development of innovative processes and products.
- RT3 Circular economy, where the goals will be that of developing novel foods, feeds, and ingredients derived from agricultural by-products through efficient recovery processes; conducting life cycle assessments (LCA) and devise tools and technologies for assessing nutritional value, and, finally, evaluating the economic viability and market appeal of utilizing by-products, incorporating consumer perception studies.
- RT4 Logistics, supply chain and vertical coordination with the aim of analyzing the sustainability and circular economy practices in agri-food firms across the supply chain and develop suitable data management platforms. Moreover, there will be focus on developing novel technologies for sustainable supply chain through management, integration, transparency, and authenticity of large amount of heterogenous data.,

In this scientific context, Cross-Cutting Activity 1 plays an important role in fostering a coordinated and transversal approach across all Spokes within the iNEST project. Aligned with the framework of an innovation ecosystem, this activity serves the purpose of valorizing innovative ideas arising from the research activities of Spoke 7 and facilitating the generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs.

7.2. SPOKE 7 CCI TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

The Specialists Franco Bocchini, Gianni Tortella, and Valter Carturo have been involved in the iNEST project since January 1, 2024, thanks to the following two Calls:

- Call for selection AdR4344/23 based on qualifications and interview for the formulation of a ranking list for the awarding of one research grant in the scientific-disciplinary sector ING-INF/05 INFORMATION PROCESSING SYSTEM
- Call for selection AdR4300/23 based on qualifications and interview for the formulation of a ranking list for the awarding of two research grants in the scientific-disciplinary sector AGR/01 ECONOMICS AND RURAL APPRAISAL

Keeping in mind that we must run, as UniVR started this activity only in mid-December with the Christmas holidays approaching, the first phase focuses on scouting ideas from researchers and students, not only looking at the evaluation by the Scientific Commission next March, but also at the second round, a year later. This activity, therefore, is still ongoing.

In the meantime, there is also a second phase: it is called pre-acceleration and it consists of support for the initial development of all the proposed projects that really aim to reach the market - in order to provide the fundamental set of information and, then, make a choice between them for centralized assessment - provided by experienced professionals of start-up mentoring and from the investment industry, now involved in Univr.

7.3. SPOKE 7 CCI DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

(e.g., conferences, meetings, participation in kick-off and mid-term plenary sessions, overall working group activities, interaction with the stakeholders)

On 13th December 2023 the “handshake meeting” was the first involving UniVR experts. From that day on, the collaboration with UniVE - which has the role of coordinator for this scouting and pre-acceleration phase - and the whole iNEST structure usefully began. The Liaison Office of UniVR, able to launch a “call for ideas” and effective in talking with professors and researchers is precious part of the team too and an action to reach interested Departments was immediately planned

7.4. SPOKE 7 CCI MAIN RESULTS

(main results achieved till now, including pictures, photos, graphs, table, link to on-line material, etc...)

Due to the late start, no result could be reached within December, but January is rich of activities: the Specialists have started and will continue to meet weekly (every Monday) with the technical staff of the Liaison Office, represented by Simone Sprea and Valentina Nicolini, and with Dr. Maria Gabaldo, Research Area Manager of the University of Verona, with the aim is collecting responses and feedback from the preliminary entrepreneurial ideas scouting activity, targeting not only professors, doctoral students, PhD graduates, and graduates, but also students.

7.5. **ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN**

(Bullet points and brief summary, administration topics)

Apart from the well known late start, a problem could be the lack of fascination for the already structured spin-offs, unable to understand what advantage could they get, without a “real money” injection: to overcome this, the main answer regards the wideness of the relationships in the system, able to open more doors than at present.

7.6. **NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES**

(With reference to the 2024 activities)

On January 22, 2024, a plenary session will be held in UniVR involving the Program Leader, the Program Manager, the Scouting Officer, the Scouting Officer Assistants, some Committee Members, and Scouting Specialists from all the spokes, as well as the Event Communication Specialist, during which the roadmap for Task CC1.2 will be decided and planned. During the session, the work plan for scouting and pre-acceleration will be shared, along with the working tools such as (Drive CC1_preAcc, literature repository, pre-screening repository, application form, presentation template). The Communication Plan for Task CC1.2 will be presented, with reference to the planned activities for Spoke 7.

The next step, after the ongoing activities and the evaluation by the iNEST Commission, is what we call the Acceleration Program, with UniVR in charge of the coordination.

8. SPOKE 8 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1 (6 pages)

The research activities of Spoke 8 address current issues in the sectors of maritime, marine and inland water technologies: towards the digital twin of the Upper Adriatic. These are supported and enhanced by five Research Topics (RTs), namely:

- **RT1** Biology of hydrosphere ecosystems
- **RT2** Physical-chemical risks and impacts on the hydrosphere
- **RT3** Sustainable waterway mobility
- **RT4** Land-sea integrated maritime and spatial Planning
- **RT5** North Adriatic Digital twin

In this scientific context, the **cross-cutting activity 1** plays an important role in fostering a coordinated and transversal approach across all Spokes within the iNEST project. Aligned with the framework of an innovation ecosystem, this activity serves the purpose of valorizing innovative ideas arising from the research activities of the Spoke 8 and facilitating the generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs.

8.1. SPOKE 8 CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

(title of the task, brief description of the topics, participants, general organisation and planning, expected results)

CC1.2: Scouting and pre-acceleration activities

The Spoke 8 CC1.2 activities are meant at supporting the creation and development of entrepreneurial ideas on different topics, with the goal of promoting the growth of start-ups and spin-offs particularly in the territory of Friuli-Venezia Giulia. Thanks to the continuous cooperation between UniTS and PoloAA, the variegated initiatives undertaken in the context of CC1.2 aimed at enhancing territorial development and reinforcing synergies for the consolidation of innovative entrepreneurship efforts. In the context of the innovation-oriented and productive academic research environment of the territorial area where the Spoke 8 is located, the CC1.2 pre-acceleration and scouting activities were intended to collect emerging entrepreneurial ideas, select them and provide the most promising ones with the basic tools for the development and flourishing of their innovative potential, thus allowing them to turn into start-ups and spin-offs.

The scouting and pre-acceleration stages intended to foster the participation of academic students, PhD candidates, researchers, professionals and pre-seed start-ups in Calls for Startup Early Stages and for Researchers, where all participants that applied had the possibility to receive dedicated feedback

on the points of strength and to be improved of their entrepreneurial ideas. A side objective of the CC1.2 initiative in our case has been to involve as a wide public as possible to raise participants' awareness on the key concepts of innovation and entrepreneurship.

Consequently, by participating in the above-mentioned Calls for Startups, each contributor was given the opportunity to transform his/her own idea into a structured entrepreneurial project thanks to dedicated support material leading to a higher definition of the proposal.

On these bases, the aim of the scouting phase is to promote high-quality ideas which show real potential for funding, by equipping future start-up founders with a basic toolbox of essential knowledge and skills for entrepreneurship. As a matter of fact, the ultimate objective of this stage consists in preparing the selected candidates to pitch their ideas during the Selection Day, after which the best ones will access the Acceleration phase.

Lastly, along with the other pre-acceleration and scouting activities directly involving participants, the Spoke 8 CCI initiatives are also meant to establish fruitful relationships with other ongoing startups, companies and partners who could play a role in facilitating the development of new projects, spin-offs, and co-innovation activities to the benefit of all stakeholders involved.

8.2. SPOKE 8 CCI TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

List of CCI Tasks:

- CC1.1: Planning and validation
- **CC1.2: Pre-acceleration**
 - Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 9-40
 - Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 10-23
 - Sub Task CC1.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 12-26
 - Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities. the objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners in order to facilitate the development

of new projects, spinoffs and co-innovation activities between universities, startups and companies.

Responsible: UNIUD

Duration: months 9-40

- CC1.3: Acceleration
- CC1.4: Fundraising

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and pre-acceleration activities in the Spoke "8"

Background / State of the Art: On October 11th, 2023 PoloAA (Perin, Santaliana) met UNITS (Bortoluzzi, Dore) in Trieste to share information on CC1 pre-acceleration phase and define a workplan to respect the project timeline. On October 27th, 2023 a meeting was held in Pordenone: it was dedicated to CC1 with the coordination of UNIVE and all other actors of INEST in Friuli Venezia Giulia: in that occasion the workplan drafted by UNITS and POLOAA has been presented and adopted as example on how to implement the pre-acceleration activities in the other Spokes. The last background information to define the state of the art is the online meeting organized by UNIVE on December 14th, 2023 in order to present all the scouting specialists of the various Spokes and align their activities. Regarding Spoke 8, Tiziana Perin has been indicated as scouting specialist by PoloAA and Salvatore Dore by UNITS.

Methodology: Based on the meetings above mentioned, the methodology to carry on the Task CC1.2 for Spoke 8 comprised the following activities:

1. Online (PoloAA newsletter, Facebook and LinkedIn) and offline (PoloAA premises) promotion of the open call for early stage start up and researchers (second half of October 2023) through two dedicated posters with a QR code linking to a google form where to present the problem addressed and the idea proposed in 2.000 characters.

2. Direct emails with invitations have also been sent to the first three groups that won the 2 hackathons organized within INEST events in 2023 (see paragraph 2.3): ICC FVG accelerator and Summer Hacktown, so to give to the winners a concrete opportunity to work on their ideas and possibly be funded.
3. 08/11/2023 Event MEET STARTUPS AND LAUNCH YOUR ONES! organized by PoloAA and UNITS at Alea Pro Digital premises (Pordenone) with the following agenda:

14.00 Arrival and registration

14.20 Presentation of PoloAA – *Tiziana Perin, Polo Tecnologico Alto Adriatico, Pordenone*

14.30 Presentation of local START-UPS with Q&A (25 min. each)

1. EFFICIENTA – Energia, Innovazione, Sostenibilità - *Daniele Florean, CEO*
2. AGABUNA – *Luca Truant, general manager*
3. BIOFUTURE MEDICINE - *Flavio Rizzolio, CEO*
4. VITESY – *Paolo Ganis, CEO*

16.10 Break

16.25 iNEST Project (Interconnected Nord-Est Innovation Ecosystem),
CC1: Support to the generation and the development of start-ups and s
Università Ca' Foscari, Venezia

16.40 CALL for STARTUPPERS WANNABE: QR scan and submit you
Università degli Studi di Trieste

17.00 Interaction with the students: “What kind of idea have you presented? Let’s talk about it!” -
Guido Bortoluzzi, Università degli Studi di Trieste
17.30 Leaving for Trieste

75 students of prof. Bortoluzzi course ‘Management of Innovation’ participated and had the chance to:

- Get to know INEST project with a focus on CCI activities
- Get to know 4 innovative startups of the territory and their business model
- Present their own ideas for a startup based on the google form created for the submission
- Engage in an analysis of the 4 start-ups presented during the event, which gave participants the chance to apply what read on the books to concrete business cases and directly hear entrepreneurs' witnesses on their real-world experiences.

Engagement/Scouting **What**

CALL

8 novembre EVENTO PRESSO

ALEA PRO DIGITAL – PORDENONE

CON 75 STUDENTI UNITS

4. The third key activity organized to engage students in presenting business ideas has been the event series “INEST Business Model Game Labs – Laboratori d’Innovazione”, from November 27th to December 1st, 2023. In this occasion, participants were initially given an introduction on the INEST project and the CLAB activities. Then, the core of the workshops consisted in promoting the development and the definition of the participants’ entrepreneurial ideas thanks to the Business Model Game LEAP. Workshops were open to UNITS students and researchers from all fields and allowed even non-experienced participants to craft and adjust their innovative ideas in an interactive and collaborative manner, both with the facilitators and with other participants.

Ongoing activities: While drafting this deliverable, the ongoing activity of UNITS-POLOAA in CC1.2 is the second slot of the event “INEST Business Model Game Labs – Laboratori d’Innovazione”, which is taking place this same week, specifically on 17-18-19 of January 2024. Like in the first edition, the students that will participate in this event, will be invited to present their idea through our online google form, accessible via QR code: subsequently they will be reported in the common repository provided by UNIVE and will be pre-screened by Spoke 8 scouting specialists within the last week of January. Following this, we will have our final panel of students and researchers that will access to the next step of evaluation through the submission of the selection form and the pitch deck with deadline 15.02.2024, if the material for the tuition will be uploaded in a convenient time to allow the students to have tools for deepening how to present their idea. So far, we have collected 60 ideas, out of which 57 from the activities previously described and 3 from researchers of UNITS who participated in INEST events and were informed of the project’s opportunities.

We provided first general feedback via email to all the 60 participants, with one-to-one observations underlining positive aspects and things to be implemented in their proposal both from a technical and economic point of view. Besides, we invited them to participate in the Contamination Lab (CLAB), which is the University's hub for innovative ideas and aims at fostering the development of entrepreneurial skills for students and professionals. As the founding and creation of new enterprises is among the CLAB overarching goals, it is indeed the best place where to provide students with the tools and competences necessary for the development of successful business ideas.

8.3. SPOKE 8 CCI DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

(e.g., conferences, meetings, participation in kick-off and mid-term plenary sessions, overall working group activities, interaction with the stakeholders)

The dissemination activities put in place by POLOAA and UNITS for iNEST CC1 in some cases overlap with the activities described in 2.2: besides those already described, we had other 2 meetings where CC1 activities were presented:

- November 21st, 2023 in Trieste c/o University (information about the CC1 to all University departments)
- December 19th, 2023 in Trieste c/o University (information about all iNEST activities to the whole iNEST consortium and stakeholders of the Spoke 8)

All the work carried on by prof. Bortoluzzi with his students on the 4 innovative start-ups presented during the event c/o Alea Pro on November 8th 2023, represents a good example of working with and engagement of stakeholders for the CC1. Afterwards, the students were split in group and assigned to one of the 4 startups, with the task of exploring in depth their business models through knowledge and tools learnt during the 'Management of Innovation' course. Consequently, they could directly learn from

Under iNEST activities, University of Trieste also organized:

- An event called Blockchain Innovation day 2.0 on November 27th, 2023
- A series of seminars on intellectual property and valorisation of the research results, in collaboration with Area Science Park (26.10.23-23.11.23-18.01.24)
- C-LAB seminars (from 25.10.23 to 20.12.23)
- C-LAB final event (19.12.23)
- Under CC1 foreseen events, PoloAA within the Spoke 8 competencies and themes, organized two hackathons, with the direct participation of almost 100 students competing for presenting the best idea, supported by a huge network of local and international stakeholders, as mentors and jury (regional representatives, political and technical figures of the Municipality of Pordenone, teachers from various European Universities, CEOs of companies, digital strategists and informatics, business angels, etc.):
 - Hackathon FVG ICC Accelerator, 22-23/05/23. All information can be found here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ysQrYpL2JLI&list=PLJ9xn0eU5enXx-cXo3CBe3XBtRDQ5ThNB>
 - Summer Hacktown 2023, 30/08/23-02/09/23. All information can be found here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dyiGZ0IUrd0&list=PLJ9xn0eU5enUdUJxG8z6hfqGNzaEqOefN>

8.4. SPOKE 8 CC1 MAIN RESULTS

(main results achieved till now, including pictures, photos, graphs, table, link to on-line material, etc.)

First of all, the variegated CC1 activities conducted in the context of Spoke 8 have empowered participants with the tools to better elaborate and present their entrepreneurial ideas. Direct students' involvement, indeed, has led to substantial positive impacts on their education on entrepreneurship and innovation, both from theoretical and practical standpoints. As a matter of fact, interdisciplinary and engaging activities contributed to enrich the learning environment, giving participants diverse perspectives and practical insights on entrepreneurship and innovation opportunities. Thus, the interactive learning initiatives overall improved participants' understanding of real-world case studies, enhanced their comprehension of business concepts and contributed to broaden their knowledge on relevant topics for entrepreneurial culture, technological and territorial growth which also stand as key components of sustainable development.

Furthermore, the diversification of activities allowed to reach a wider target audience and collect more than 60 fruitful innovative ideas from participants on several diversified topics, too. Together with the opportunity to candidate entrepreneurial ideas online, also the possibility to access dedicated and responsive physical support during the creative phase also constituted an added value to students' understanding and learning.

Along with specific education on the above-mentioned topics, the Spoke 8 CCI activities also promoted the development of practical and soft skills, such as problem-solving, team building and effective communication. These, in turn, contribute to shape the open-minded and flexible attitudes which are not only useful in everyday life, but are increasingly valued for job opportunities.

Lastly, the need to craft interdisciplinary education material and maximise the innovation potential of the collected entrepreneurial ideas also enhanced collaboration among the different stakeholders involved. Thus, the reinforcement of cooperation among diversified key actors for territorial and social development purposes is also to be included among the most important successes of the CCI activities of the Spoke 8.

Overall, the results remark the transformative impact of entrepreneurial education within the broader context of the project objectives. By boosting the growth of a new generation of innovative and socially responsible entrepreneurs, the CCI activities of the Spoke 8 contributed significantly to the development of a dynamic, responsive, and inclusive innovative ecosystem.

8.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

(Bullet points and brief summary, administration topics)

- Coordination of the initiatives across the universities part of the INEST project:** the CCI activities were not simultaneously conducted within each Spoke, due to diverse organisational arrangements and responsible teams for each involved University. This led to asymmetrical information collected during some activities across the partner universities, as well as to the need to delay the follow-up stages of the entrepreneurial training in order to avoid too many differences in advancement levels across the involved academic entities. Nevertheless, good communication among the INEST academic institutions allowed to promptly promote corrective actions for scouting activities ahead, ensuring better planning and higher coordination efforts among the academic innovation labs involved for the prosecution of CCI activities.
- Formal academic communication of the CCI initiatives:** the need for institutional communication of the activities sometimes led to advertisement delays of the very same activities. Due to the wide inter-departmental involvement of actors in the context of INEST, bureaucratic academic procedures sometimes prevented adequate engagement actions in terms of social media advertisement and interdepartmental information. This, in turn, led to inadequate information on the initiatives provided to potentially interested participants. Nevertheless, it is necessary to admit that, despite the delays due to administrative needs, the activities were highly appreciated by participants. In this case, too, reactive and fruitful confrontation among the involved actors allowed for higher responsiveness and better coordination during the subsequent round of activities.

8.6. **NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES** (With reference to the 2024 activities)

The activities foreseen in 2024 are the following:

1. End of January 2024: A second email will be sent when the last collection of ideas will be completed with the 'INEST Business Model Game Labs' edition of this current week. In this next email we will expose the tuition program and give access to all the online training foreseen in the project, in order to help the participants in defining better their idea through the Selection Form and Pitch Deck for the second stage of selection scheduled in the second half of February.
2. February 2024: close the pre-selection of startups ideas and researcher's spin offs within Spoke 8
3. Participate in the Selection Day common to all the Spokes, with the 4+ startups selected in Spoke 8
4. Engage the winning ideas of the Spoke 8 in the acceleration programme according to the timeline set by the coordinator UNIVE (end of Milestone 14)
5. Start the second round of startup involvement (Milestone 15) with the beginning of the prof. Bortoluzzi's course in Entrepreneurship and Business Modelling, which will be held during the 2nd semester of the academic year 2023/2024.

References

Contamination lab. (n.d.). Università Degli Studi Di Trieste. <https://www.units.it/clab>

Facilitator Toolbox // The Business Model game. (n.d.). LEAP - the Business Model Game. <https://www.businessmodelgame.com/en/facilitator-toolbox>

9. SPOKE 9 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1 (6 pages)

The research activities of Spoke 9 address current issues in the sectors of mathematical and numerical models, scientific computing, and digital twins. These are supported and enhanced by four Research Topics (RTs), namely:

- **RT1 - Mathematical, Numerical and Data-driven Modeling**, which aims to create a framework for the mathematical modeling of complex systems, i.e. a mathematical description of systems composed of many interacting parts;
- **RT2 - Model Order Reduction**, an advanced numerical approach that is employed to reduce the computational cost of numerical simulations;
- **RT3 - Automatic Learning for Digital Twins**, devoted to the application of automatic learning techniques, such as machine learning and reduced order models, in a high-performance computing setting;
- **RT4 - Applications of DT in Industry, Medicine, Environmental Sciences, Daily life**, whose goal is to review the most updated techniques regarding the applications of digital twins to the environment, daily life, and infrastructures.

In this scientific context, **Cross-Cutting Activity 1** plays an important role in fostering a coordinated and transversal approach across all Spokes within the iNEST project. Aligned with the framework of an innovation ecosystem, this activity serves the purpose of valorizing innovative ideas arising from the research activities of Spoke 9 and facilitating the generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs.

9.1. SPOKE 9 CCI OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

Within the iNEST Consortium, the overall goal of Cross-Cutting Activity 1 is to promote the generation and the selection of innovative ideas emerging from the scientific activities of Spoke 9 and to transform them into research start-ups and spin-offs. To this aim, CCI is subdivided into four distinct phases.

The first phase of CCI concerns the planning and the validation of all activities. This involved the hiring of dedicated personnel to support the activities as planned by the committee of the CCI.

Currently, CCI has entered its second phase, namely the Pre-acceleration phase. The main objective of Spoke 9 is now to encourage doctoral students, researchers, and pre-seed start-uppers to submit their applications for the **Call for Start-up Pre-seed** - the application form where they can present their early entrepreneurial ideas - which will then be selected and turned into start-up projects. To pursue this main objective, several actions and corresponding sub-goals have been identified:

- members of already existing **pre-seed start-ups** have to be contacted individually, to inform them about CCI and encourage their application for the Call. The Scouting Specialist is entrusted with this one-to-one communication to existing start-ups;

- **doctoral students** and **researchers** have to learn about CCI, as well as be encouraged to share their ideas through the Call, thanks to engagement activities, and promotional operations that have to be prepared by an Event Communication Specialist and an Event Communication Assistant.

Moreover, every outreach activity has to be disseminated on public communication platforms such as institutional websites and social media pages, as well as those of the iNEST Consortium and the [Spoke 9 website](#), which is under the direct supervision of the Event Communication Specialist and the Event Communication Assistant. The goal is to contact **10** start-ups, of which at least **5** are expected to apply for the Call up to its deadline, corresponding to mid-February 2024. The engagement activities and promotional operations are also aimed at receiving **15** applications from students and researchers.

9.2. SPOKE 9 CCI TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

List of CCI Tasks:

- CCI.1: Planning and validation
- **CCI.2: Pre-acceleration**
 - Sub Task CCI.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 9-40
 - Sub Task CCI.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 10-23
 - Sub Task CCI.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 12-26
 - Sub Task CCI.2.4: Open innovation activities. The objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners in order to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs, and co-innovation activities between universities, startups, and companies.
Responsible: UNIUD
Duration: months 9-40
- CCI.3: Acceleration

- CC1.4: Fundraising

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and pre-acceleration activities in the Spoke 9

Background/State of the Art: The activities of CC1 within Spoke 9 are supported by the Valorisation and Innovation Office of SISSA. Technology and knowledge transfer are considered crucial and strategic activities, and concrete and structured actions are taken systemically to promote innovation, valorize internal research and talents, and improve the impact of the research results on society and the productive and economic ecosystem. For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.2.1**, the following figures have been selected:

- Alberto Cavazza, who covers the role of Scouting Specialist for Spoke 9;
- Luca Mingotti Landriani, who covers the role of Event Communication Specialist;
- Sara Anzuinelli, who covers the role of Event Communication Assistant.

The Scouting Specialist participated in a series of initiatives promoted by the Scouting Officer with the aim of training and preparing these reference figures of the nine Spokes. Moreover, the Scouting Specialist contributed to the generation of the literature research repository together with colleagues of the other Spokes with the aim to map the state of the art. The topics explored by the Spoke 9 Scouting Specialist concern: innovation ecosystems, open innovation, company-university collaboration, Technology Transfer, and the Digital Twin business model.

As for **Sub-task CC1.2.2**, the implementation of the Scouting Stage has begun with the preparation of the Call for Start-up Pre-seed by the Scouting Specialist of Spoke 9, under the supervision of the Scouting Officer and of the Assistant Scouting Officers. With the beginning of the Pre-acceleration phase, the contribution of the Valorisation and Innovation Office of SISSA has been recognised as fundamental, in particular to guide the Scouting Specialist to attract internal doctoral students and researchers potentially interested in proposing their ideas. Regarding **Sub-task CC1.2.3**, the development of the educational repository for aspiring startupper has initially been rooted in a collection of state-of-the-art learning objects from benchmarks: these clips display practical lectures on how to conceive, launch, fund, and lead a start-up. These videos are meant to provide basic notions about entrepreneurship and start-up generation and development. **Sub-task CC1.2.4** is currently under the guidance of Spoke 3 and will not be covered in the following. Nevertheless, regarding Spoke 9 the activities of such sub-task will be carried out in agreement with the Valorisation and Innovation Office of SISSA.

Methodology: For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.2.2**, all the applications for the Call for Start-up Pre-seed were collected in a common database. Potential startupper were contacted by the Scouting Specialist to organize a series of one-to-one meetings to explore together the potential of innovative ideas and research results to valorize. Furthermore, the opportunity to apply for the Call for Start-up Pre-seed has been advertised using different channels, such as e-mails from the Valorisation and Innovation Office of SISSA and through the [news on the Spoke 9 website](#). Regarding **Sub-task CC1.2.3**, the tuition materials have been selected using benchmarking criteria involving the top worldwide business schools and universities, making sure that they are freely and publicly available.

Ongoing activities: As for **Sub-task CC1.2.2**, the Call for Start-up Pre-seed has been publicly accessible since the beginning of December 2023. Regarding the Pre-acceleration phase, in recent weeks the Scouting Specialist has started one-to-one meetings with each potential startupper to support them in compiling the pitch deck, a fundamental element of the selection phase. Moreover, the Event Communication Specialist and the Event Communication Assistant have been working on the organization of a networking session for doctoral students and researchers, to inform them about how to approach the world of start-ups, to encourage their participation in the CC1, and their application for the Call for Start-up pre-seed. The networking session, named “iNEST Meet&Drink”, will be held at SISSA on 17th January 2024. Moreover, this event is currently being promoted through several actions, such as e-mails from the Valorisation and Innovation Office, the SISSA and Spoke 9 websites, social media pages, and students’ Telegram channels. As far as **Sub-task CC1.2.3** is concerned, the tuition contents for entrepreneurial training are currently under development according to the Scouting Specialist, Scouting Officer, and the Scouting Officer Assistants guiding lines. Contents will be focused on knowledge units’ clips introducing how-to-use the pitch template with thorough explanations of Academic Mentors.

9.3. SPOKE 9 CC1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

On **27th October 2023**, a plenary session involving the Program Leader, the Program Manager, the Scouting Officer, the Scouting Officer Assistants, some Committee Members and Scouting Specialists from other Spokes, and the Event Communication Specialist was held, in which the roadmap for Task CC1.2 was decided and planned. Specifically, during the session:

- the plan for the construction of the shared methodological frame was validated;
- the first test for Scouting activities of project partners belonging to the Friuli-Venezia Giulia area was reported;
- the common process of selection and pre-acceleration of start-ups/ideas was reviewed;
- the management of communication and open innovation have been discussed.

On **13th December 2023**, an online handshake meeting involving the Scouting Officer, the Scouting Officer Assistants, the Scouting Specialists from all Spokes, the Event Communication Specialist, and the Event Communication Assistant was held. During the meeting:

- the Scouting Specialists explained what they were working on;
- the status of the work, namely the process and shared tools (Drive CC1_preAcc, Literature repository, Pre-screening repository, Application Form, Pitch Deck template), was presented;
- the differentiation of the Call according to the audiences (students, researchers, start-ups) has been discussed;
- updates on the Tuition program and training were provided;
- the Communication Plan for Task CC1.2 was presented, with a reference to the activities planned for Spoke 9.

Every CC1 activity in which Spoke 9 is involved has been programmed and designed by a team consisting of the Scouting Officer, the Scouting Officer Assistants, the Scouting Specialist, the Event Communication Specialist, the Event Communication Assistant, and SISSA Press Officers, with the supervision of Prof. Gianluigi Rozza (Spoke 9 representative) and Prof. Giovanni Noselli (CC1 Committee

Member for Spoke 9). This team reunited in a number of meetings, sometimes involving the members of the Valorisation and Innovation Office (Dr. Renè Butto) and of the Communication Office (Dr. Nico Pitrelli and Dr. Chiara Saviane).

The organization of iNEST Meet&Drink also requested to contact two SISSA start-up CEOs: Andrea Martini from FAST Computing and Enrico Siagri from MATERYS. Indeed, their presence will be crucial to help students and researchers understand how it is possible to pursue an entrepreneurial career starting from the world of academic research. Note that the Program Leader, the Scouting Officer, and the Scouting Officer Assistants will also be present at the networking session.

For what concerns the public communication of Task CC1.2, besides promotional operations aimed at advertising both the Call and the iNEST Meet&Drink networking session, the Event Communication Specialist and the Event Communication Assistant have been working on a [brief description of CC1](#) for the Spoke 9 website, as well as [news articles](#) that have been shared on the SISSA and iNEST Consortium websites as well. iNEST Meet&Drink will be a great opportunity to showcase the interest in CC1 through other news articles and social media posts.

9.4. SPOKE 9 CC1 MAIN RESULTS

Until now, 5 potential startupperes have been contacted by the Scouting Specialist through an introductory meeting aimed at getting in touch with them. The Scouting Specialist has been oriented by the SISSA Valorisation and Innovation Office towards 2 existing researchers and doctoral students interested in the possibility of enhancing their research activity through the creation of a start-up. Moreover, 3 doctoral students contacted the Valorisation and Innovation Office after the launch of the Call for Start-up Pre-seed to learn more about the project and propose their ideas. They were also contacted by the Scouting Specialist and started a pre-acceleration process aimed at preparing the pitch deck useful for the selection phase and filling out the application form.

The potential startupperes are now preparing the first part of the pitch deck dedicated to the problem description and the solution proposal using quantitative and qualitative information. Some candidates are focusing on the description of the start-up impact from the environmental and social point of view; moreover, they are identifying the target market and the competitors that currently populate this market.

The candidates were also involved in the initiatives organized by the Valorisation and Innovation Office to increase the entrepreneurial culture within the institute, such as the networking session that will be held on 17th January at SISSA.

9.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

Some problems were encountered in the initial part of the planning and programming of the activity and were given by the need to better integrate the activities already carried out by the Valorisation and Innovation Office of SISSA with the context of CC1. These were resolved with a number of coordination meetings that made it possible to start a synergistic activity between the Valorisation and Innovation Office and the Scouting Specialist. The Scouting Specialist weekly reports to Dr. Tanja Lunardelli, who

is the figure dedicated to internal scouting in SISSA, the continuation of the activities, the response of the people met, and the potential issues to be addressed regarding the protection and patenting of ideas.

A key challenge for Task CC1.2 is the engagement of doctoral students and researchers, as these are typically unaware of the possibilities of the entrepreneurial world and are focused on a more academic path. To do so, it is crucial to highlight the value of their ideas, even if they are still not structured in a way that makes them viable as start-up projects.

9.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

The upcoming event on 17th January will provide insight into the general interest of SISSA doctoral students and researchers in CC1. By monitoring its turnout, it will be possible to understand whether further dissemination and promotional actions are needed to increase the number of submissions.

After the event, the challenge will be to meet new potential start-uppers through one-to-one meetings to get to know them and discuss their idea with the Scouting Specialist. This will be the last step before the preparation of the pitch deck and the completion of the application form by the largest number of start-uppers contacted in the previous phases.

In mid-February 2024, the Call for Start-up Pre-seed will be closed, and the most promising ideas will be selected and brought to the Selection Day that will take place in late February/early March 2024 in the form of start-up pitches. The selected ones will then access the Acceleration phase, which pertains to Task CC1.3, and the Fundraising phase, corresponding to Task CC1.4.

References

We report here the list of the links to the webpages relevant to Spoke 9 and in particular to Cross-Cutting Activity 1:

- The website dedicated to the [Spoke 9](#);
- A brief description of [CC1](#) within Spoke 9;
- Advertisement of the [Call for Start-up pre-seed](#);
- Advertisement of the event [iNEST Meet&Drink](#).